

poiesis
TRUST IN SCIENCE

D2.4: Survey Experiment

Author(s): *Simon Fuglsang (AU)*

Reviewer(s): *Anne-Sophie Behm-Bahtat (WiD)*

Project title: Probing the impact of integrity and integration on societal trust in science

Project acronym: POIESIS

Grant Agreement no.:101057253

Lead partner for this deliverable Aarhus University

Deliverable factsheet:

Project Number:	101057253
Project Acronym:	POIESIS
Project Title:	Probing the impact of integrity and integration on societal trust in science
Title of Deliverable:	D2.4: Survey experiment
Work Package:	WP2
Due date according to contract:	31 December 2024
Actual delivery date:	15 January 2025
	Probing the impact of integrity and integration on societal trust in science
Author(s):	Simon Fuglsang (AU)
Reviewer:	Anne-Sophie Behm-Bahtat (WiD)

ABSTRACT:	<p>The POIESIS survey experiment investigates how trust is affected by institutional commitment to research integrity and societal integration. It does so in a conjoint experiment, in which participants rate the trustworthiness of fictional universities, which are randomly assigned levels of integrity and integration commitments. The study is fielded among a sample of 2800 participants (400 participants in each of the seven POIESIS partner countries). The findings indicate that institutional commitments toward research integrity and societal integration causes higher trustworthiness evaluations. Furthermore, providing additional information on the reputation of the fictional universities does not notably change the effects of commitments to integrity and integration. However, while participants are sensitive to institutional commitments to research integrity and societal integration, they are less sensitive to specificities regarding the level or form of commitment. Effects are present across all included countries, though the exact patterns in magnitude of specific commitments varies across context. Across respondent characteristics effects are largely consistent, with the notable exception of prior trust in science. Specifically, effects are only present for individuals who indicate having at least some trust in science prior to the experiment.</p>
Keyword List:	POIESIS, Trust in Science, Research Integrity, Societal Integration, Institutional Commitment, Survey Experiment

Consortium:

	ROLE	NAME	Short Name	Country
1.	Coordinator	AARHUS UNIVERSITY	AU	Denmark
2.	Partner	WISSENSCHAFT IM DIALOG GGMBH	WiD	Germany
3.	Partner	NATIONAL TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF ATHENS	NTUA	Greece
4.	Partner	INSTITUTO UNIVERSITÁRIO DE LISBOA	ISCTE	Portugal
5.	Partner	CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE	CNRS	France
6.	Partner	AGENCIA ESTATAL CONSEJO SUPERIOR DE INVESTIGACIONES CIENTIFICAS	CSIC	Spain
7.	Associated partner	LONDON SCHOOL OF ECONOMICS AND POLITICAL SCIENCE	LSE	UK

Revision history:

VERSION	DATE	Revised by	Reason
0.1	27/11/2024	Simon Fuglsang	First draft
0.2	07/01/2025	Anne-Sophie Behm-Bahtat	Review of first draft
1.0	14/7/2025	Simon Fuglsang	Final version

Table of Contents

Executive Summary	6
1 Introduction	7
1.1 About POIESIS	7
1.2 About the POIESIS Survey experiment	8
2 Theoretical and conceptual considerations	10
2.1 Hypotheses and research questions	10
2.2 Relation to prior literature	11
2.3 Definitions and operationalizations of the core concepts	12
3 Methodology	14
3.1 Experimental design	14
3.2 Survey flow	16
3.3 Integrity considerations	17
3.4 Implementation	18
4 Findings	20
4.1 Descriptives	20
4.2 Main analyses	23
4.2.1 The effects of research integrity and societal integration	24
4.2.2 Country differences	25
4.2.3 The moderating role of reputation	27
4.3 Exploratory analyses	28
4.3.1 Comparing effects across importance of trustworthiness dimensions	29
4.3.2 Heterogenous effects across attitudes	31
4.3.3 Heterogeneous effects across sociodemographics	33
4.3.4 Time and order effects	36
4.3.5 Cross-attribute interactions	39
5 Discussion and conclusions	40
6 References	43
7 Appendix	46
7.1 Questionnaires in all languages	46
7.1.1 English (Master)	46
7.1.2 German	51
7.1.3 Danish	55
7.1.4 Spanish	59

7.1.5	French	64
7.1.6	Greek	68
7.1.7	Portuguese	73
7.2	Pre-registration	78
7.3	Regression outputs for main analyses	81
7.3.1	Main regressions	81
7.3.2	Per country regressions	82
7.3.3	Cross-reputation interactions	83
7.4	Figure 4.2.1, results per country	86
7.5	Reputation interactions with non-simplified treatments	90

Table of Figures

Figure 3.1.1: Example of a randomly generated university profile from the experiment.	15
Figure 3.1.2: Ranking of the influence of dimensions of trustworthiness in the experimental tasks.....	16
Figure 3.2.1: Survey flow.....	17
Figure 4.1.1: Sociodemographic characteristics of participants split by country.....	21
Figure 4.1.2: Prior attitudes of participants split by country.....	22
Figure 4.1.3: Trustworthiness ratings of university profiles and rating time in the experimental tasks split by country.....	23
Figure 4.2.1: Effects of integrity, integration, and reputation on trustworthiness ratings.	24
Figure 4.2.2: Effects of integrity, integration, and reputation split by country.	26
Figure 4.2.3: Effects of integrity and integration commitment split by reputation levels	28
Figure 4.3.1.1: Ranked importance of trustworthiness dimension in experimental task.....	29
Figure 4.3.1.2: Effects of integrity, integration, and reputation split by most important dimension of trustworthiness.....	30
Figure 4.3.2.1: Effects of integrity, integration, and reputation split by prior attitudes.....	32
Figure 4.3.2.2: Trustworthiness ratings in experimental groups across trust in science....	33
Figure 4.3.3.1: Effects of integrity, integration, and reputation split by gender and age..	34
Figure 4.3.3.2: Effects of integrity, integration, and reputation split by education.....	35
Figure 4.3.3.3: Effects of integrity, integration, and reputation split by professional proximity to science (Are you professionally involved with science?).....	36
Figure 4.3.4.1: Effects of integrity, integration, and reputation split by time spent on experimental task and viewing order.....	37
Figure 4.3.4.2: Effect of commitment by position of attribute in the order of university attributes.....	38
Figure 4.3.5.1: Effects of integrity, integration, and reputation split by integrity and integration attributes.....	39

Executive Summary

This report presents the findings of the POIESIS survey experiment, Task 2.4 of the project Probing the Impact of Integrity and Integration on Societal Trust in Science (POIESIS, HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01 grant number 101057253).

This task designed and fielded a survey experiment in the seven POIESIS partner countries: Denmark, France, Germany, Greece, Portugal, Spain, and UK. The aim of the study was to experimentally investigate the effects of institutional commitment to research integrity and societal integration on public trust in science. To do so, we fielded a conjoint survey experiment in which levels of commitment to integrity and integration was randomly assigned to fictional university profiles. These were then evaluated by survey respondents, 400 in each country, who were asked how trustworthy they found the fictional universities.

The key conclusions of the study are that:

- Consistent with the assumptions outlined in the POIESIS model, institutional commitment towards both research integrity and societal integration produces higher trustworthiness ratings.
- However, participants are not particularly sensitive to the level of commitment but rather whether commitment is present at all. That is, participants rate institutional commitment to national recommendations as highly as commitment to strict procedures, but both of these higher than lack of commitment.
- While all included forms of research integrity and societal integration positively affect trustworthiness ratings in all included countries (Denmark, France, Germany, Greece, Portugal, Spain, and UK), patterns of magnitude vary. This indicates that while integrity and integration matter cross-contextually the specificities of their influence are sensitive to local and cultural factors.
- The effect of institutional commitment to research integrity and societal integration is generally not diminished by cues on the reputation of organizations, neither regarding their prestige nor achievements in specific fields of research. This implies that effects of commitment towards integrity and integration is not merely used as a proxy for institutional reputation but plays an independent role in shaping trust.
- The effects of institutional commitment to research integrity and societal integration are only sensitive to sociodemographic and attitudinal differences to a minor degree. However, one notable exception is prior trust in science which is highly related to the effectiveness of institutional commitment to research integrity and societal integration. Specifically, the effect of institutional commitment is confined to participants who indicate to trust science prior to the experiment (above 5 on a 0-10 scale), whereas respondents who have low levels of prior trust in science (5 or below) exhibit no differences in trustworthiness ratings across levels of institutional commitment.

1 Introduction

This deliverable outlines the approach and findings of the POIESIS survey experiment. The study is a part of POIESIS (Probing the impact of integrity and integration on societal trust in science) funded by the European Commission under the Horizon Europe scheme (grant number 101057253). The POIESIS survey experiment is the final among three empirical studies in Work Package 2. The POIESIS survey experiment was conceptualized and designed from spring to early fall 2024 and fielded in October and November 2024. The scope, hypotheses, research questions, and design of the study were first outlined in the study protocol (Fuglsang, 2024), and the study was preregistered prior to fielding the survey (see Appendix 7.2).

1.1 About POIESIS

The POIESIS project investigates the relationship between research integrity, societal integration, and public trust in science. Core to this, is the interrogation of three widely held assumptions on the role of research practice and research policies in maintenance of high levels of trust in science. These assumptions were reiterated in the call that funded POIESIS, as summarized in the project proposal (POIESIS consortium, 2021, Part B, p. 2):

- First, that “... trust depends on scientists and engineers’ capacity to demonstrate high standards of research integrity and that breaches to research integrity, i.e., research misconduct or questionable research practices, will lead to mistrust.”
- Second, that “... citizen and civil society’s involvement in co-creating R&I agendas and contents makes research more relevant and responsive to society and strengthens co-ownership and trust.”
- Third, the call assumes that these markers of responsible research practices – integrity and societal integration – are “fostered by conducive institutional governance arrangements and policy environments”. The assumption is that institutions matter by enabling and supporting researchers to act responsibly.

However, as noted in the project proposal, and reaffirmed in Work Package 1 of POIESIS (Bauer et al., 2023), the level to which these assumptions reflect the reality of maintaining public trust in science are scarcely illuminated. To further our understanding of the dynamics at the core of the relationship between research institutions and public trust in science, as well as the chains of mediation that connect the two spheres, POIESIS set out to investigate four core research questions:

- RQ1: How can the nature and scale of public trust and mistrust in science be characterised and which are the factors that affect the relationship?
- RQ2: To what extent and how does the alignment of research practices with principles of research integrity (or, conversely, scientific misconduct, questionable

research practices, poor or absent science communication, and/or misinformation) impact public trust in science?

- RQ3: To what extent and how does the integration of citizens and societal stakeholders in research practices (or, conversely, lack of co-creation and open science practices) impact public trust in science?
- RQ4: To what extent and how can institutions provide policies and procedures that enable researchers to act in ways that are conducive to public trust in science?

These research questions are investigated in a series of empirical studies that form a collective body of evidence designed to provide firmer ground for evaluating and informing the assumptions highlighted above. To do so, POIESIS curates existing data and produces a rich set of new data. This deliverable outlines the design, implementation, and results of the final of these data streams, the POIESIS survey experiment.

1.2 About the POIESIS Survey experiment

The survey experiment is task 2.4 of the POIESIS project. This investigates the effect of institutional commitment towards research integrity and societal integration on societal trust in science by employing an experimental design.

Experimental designs are at their core concerned with maximizing internal validity in the interest of making causal claims. That is, it aims to ensure that an observed relationship between two variables is the result of one of these (the independent variable) exerting a causal effect on the other (the dependant variable). Experimental approaches do so by utilizing random assignment. Treatment conditions are randomly assigned to research participants, to safeguard from participant characteristics influencing who gets a certain treatment (selection) and ensure control over the direction of the relationship (simultaneity). Due to this, experiments are viewed as the golden standard for causal inference (Angrist & Pischke, 2009).

Survey experiments are among the most widely implemented types of experiments in the social sciences. In these, participants are randomly assigned to one or more conditions within a questionnaire and are then asked to answer survey questions or perform in-survey tasks. Experimental conditions are designed to stimulate certain behaviour in the participants (or be a control) and often take the form of text or visual stimuli. Due to random assignment of conditions, any variation in responses between experimental conditions can only be assigned to the difference in treatment. As a content-specific example, if participants assigned a high integrity treatment on average indicate higher trustworthiness than participants assigned a low integrity treatment, the utilization of random assignment means that we can say with certainty that the difference in trust is caused by the difference in integrity cues.

The POIESIS survey experiment employs a conjoint design, meaning that it provides multiple randomly assigned treatments simultaneously. Such designs are adept at

investigating the relative effect of multiple factors. This is especially attractive in answering the questions laid out by POIESIS, given the interest in both integrity and integration, the interplay between the two, and findings from prior steps of POIESIS that imply that these attributes are entangled with other attributes of research performing organizations.

The POIESIS survey experiment was implemented in October and November 2024 fielding the questionnaire to a minimum 400 participants in each of the seven POIESIS partner countries. In total a sample of 2847 respondents. This deliverable presents the theoretical, conceptual, and methodological considerations that formed the basis of the design (sections 2 and 3), as well as the findings and implications of the study (sections 4 and 5).

2 Theoretical and conceptual considerations

The mission of POIESIS is to probe the assumption that efforts towards research integrity and societal integration in research are foundational to public trust in science. Prior empirical efforts of the project have engaged the key actors in the relationship between society and the institutions of science, that is the public (Entradas et al., 2023), researchers and mediators of research (Woolley & Payá, 2024), and the institutional actors at the centre of securing responsible research (Dubois, 2024). While views are neither unanimous within nor between groups, all groups believe that different aspects of the institutionalization of integrity and integration are relevant to maintaining, building, or (when lacking such measures) undermining trust. However, not all aspects are seen as equally relevant for trustworthiness, and some are even seen as insignificant or potentially detrimental. Prior steps of POIESIS indicate that the assumptions highlighted in section 1.1, to some degree, resonate with the public, mediators, researchers, and institutional representatives. However, it is also clear that there is considerable nuance to the way in which stakeholders view the relationship between science and society generally, and the way in which the actions of the institutions and representatives of science matters for trust and trustworthiness specifically.

Building on both the core assumptions highlighted above and insights from prior empirical steps of POIESIS, the aim of this study is to employ experimental methods to test the causal effect of institutional commitments towards societal integration and research integrity on trust in science. This aim motivates the overarching question guiding the POIESIS survey experiment:

- What are the effects of institutional research integrity and societal integration commitments on trust in science?

2.1 Hypotheses and research questions

Embedded in this question are the two hypotheses that institutional commitment towards both research integrity and societal integration increases public trust in science. Furthermore, findings both within and outside POIESIS motivate the question of whether these dynamics are constant across countries and cultures, and prior POIESIS findings on the role of the reputation of research, researchers and research performing organizations motivate the question of whether reputation plays a role in shaping the effectiveness of integrity and integration in fostering trust (Entradas et al., 2023). This motivates the following hypotheses and research questions:

- H1 Commitment to research integrity in research performing organizations increases trust in science.

- H2 Commitment to societal integration in research performing organizations increases trust in science.
- RQ1 To which degree are effects of integrity and integration consistent across countries?
- RQ2 To which degree are effects of integrity and integration moderated by organization reputation?

2.2 Relation to prior literature

As noted in POIESIS deliverable D1.2 (Bauer et al., 2023), only limited knowledge on the role of research integrity and societal integration in forming and maintaining public trust in science exists. As such, the frame of reference for the POIESIS survey experiment is limited. A small group of experiments investigate the role of the replication crisis for trust in the field of psychology and potential remedies (Anvari & Lakens, 2019; Methner et al., 2023; Wingen et al., 2020), and a single study investigates the impact of failed and successful replications in the fictional case of a specific study on radiation (Hendriks et al., 2020). Alongside this, two studies investigate the role of special interests in research, specifically private company involvement, finding that this could deteriorate trust and willingness to engage with science (Critchley et al., 2015; Critchley, 2008). In the same vein, though with conflicting results, a single study investigates the relationship between open science practices and trust in science (Rosman et al., 2022). Less research investigates the effect of societal integration on trust in science. As noted in deliverable D1.2 (Bauer et al., 2023), some research points toward citizen science (and other forms of integration) as a potential source of trust in science, but findings are confined to specific efforts that participants generally self-select into, and to the knowledge of the author no prior experimental reference studies exist.

Common for these studies is a focus on a singular aspect of research integrity and specifically a strong focus on reproducibility. In the POIESIS survey experiment, we investigate a broad set of integrity and integration considerations simultaneously. Moreover, prior studies overwhelmingly focus on the behaviour of (groups/fields of) researchers, while largely ignoring the role of institutions and organizations. In this study, we provide new insights by turning to research performing organizations, which are key to fostering and maintaining responsible and inclusive research practice (Mejlgaard et al., 2020).

While it is impossible to incorporate the full corpus of potential integrity and integration considerations in any one study, the aim of this study is to provide insights into how key institutional commitments to such considerations resonate with members of the public. That is, do they have the trust building and/or -maintaining functions that we tend to assume they have. Moreover, the study has a particular interest in understanding how people react when competing considerations are presented simultaneously. This latter point is especially relevant given the complexities of the real-world research landscape

that members of not only the public, but also researchers, mediators, and organizations must navigate. The apparent adeptness in navigating such complexities identified in prior steps of the project (Entradas et al., 2023) motivates the expectation that members of the public are indeed able to disentangle different aspects of research integrity and societal integration, but this study presents a first experimental investigation of such an expectation.

2.3 Definitions and operationalizations of the core concepts

POIESIS adheres to an inclusive definition of research integrity as both the “core sins in science” but also “research practices, blending into research ethics and professional standards” (POIESIS consortium, 2021, Part B, p. 6). As such, research integrity is broadly defined as the adherence to ethical, legal and professional standards in research. In operationalising research integrity, the survey experiment is informed by articulation of research integrity principles both in the specialized literature (Mejlgaard et al., 2020; Ryan et al., 2021), institutional guidelines for fostering research integrity (ALLEA, 2023), and the way in which representatives of society understand and discuss research integrity in prior steps of POIESIS (Dubois, 2024; Entradas et al., 2023; Woolley & Payá, 2024). In the design of the survey experiment, this led to three focal points: First, on what we term *integrity principles*, that is commitment to “honesty, transparency, and responsibility”, these principles follow the articulation European public policy for research integrity. Second, we focus on *conflicts of interest*, which has proven to be a particularly salient theme for participants in prior studies of the POIESIS project, who see the potential for outside influence and politicization as a key integrity concern. Third, we include *diversity and inclusion* among staff to incorporate commitments to taking care of the academic work force. That is, the internal commitment to ensuring that working conditions are up to high standards. As such, in operationalization research integrity we incorporate commitment to the principles of research integrity, as well as safeguards against both external as well as internal threats to integrity.

Societal integration is defined as the inclusion of the public and stakeholders in research processes and decision-making. Once again, the project takes an inclusive approach incorporating such factors as “engagement, co-creation, open science practices” (POIESIS consortium, 2021, Part B, p. 7). As with integrity, the aim of the survey experiment is to align the operationalization of integrity not only with academic literature and institutional practice, but also the articulation of integration among participants in prior studies of POIESIS. In the design of the survey experiment, two aspects of societal integration are included: First, *hearing the public* when they are impacted by research, the commitment to make sure that the societal impact of science is considered as a part of the scientific process. Second, *communicating science* to the public, a point that was of special interest among participants in prior steps of the project (Entradas et al., 2023), capturing the commitment to making scientific insights available to society. As such, this

operationalization attempts to capture both directions of the relationship between society and science, by targeting efforts towards bringing societal concerns into science as well as efforts towards making the knowledge of science available for society.

Finally, trust in science is a concept that enjoys considerable attention in contemporary research. Dominant approaches tend to define trust or trustworthiness perceptions as a multi-dimensional concept. Specifically, the three dimensions of competence, benevolence, and integrity are well established while more recent approach additionally incorporates openness (Besley et al., 2021; Hendriks et al., 2015). Particularly integrity and openness intuitively relate to research integrity and integration in research. Due to these clear conceptual overlaps between aspects of integrity and integrations and the cited trustworthiness measures, that is the independent and dependent variables, we opt for a direct trust measure. Using a direct trustworthiness measure has the upside of not carrying the risks of conceptual overlap between the key variables, however, it also has the weakness of removing the possibility of understanding the role of different aspects of trust. To remedy this, we implement an exercise after the experiment, in which participants are asked to self-indicate which of the four dimensions of competence, benevolence, integrity, and openness (written in plain language see section 3.1) mattered most for their ratings, to investigate the connection between experiment behaviour and these theoretical models. As such, we avoid biasing the evaluations of participants through conceptual overlap between treatments and outcome but still retain the ability of investigating whether respondent behaviour follows common conceptualizations from the study of trust in science.

3 Methodology

The POIESIS survey experiment tests the causal effect of institutional commitment to research integrity and societal integration on trust in science. As such, the fundamental concern is designing treatments that provide cues indicating varying levels and forms of research integrity and societal integration commitments. Furthermore, the study tests the cross-contextual heterogeneity of such effects, which requires the implementation of the study in multiple languages. Finally, the entanglement between these integrity and integration commitments and organization reputation is of key interest, which requires the design of additional treatments that provide cues on the reputation of research performing organizations. In this section, the design of the POIESIS survey experiment, as well as the logic behind it, is presented (3.1 and 3.2). After this, the integrity considerations which were key to the design are discussed (3.3). Finally, the components and timeline of the implementation is presented (3.4).

3.1 Experimental design

To enable discrimination between the effects of multiple aspects of integration, integrity, and reputation the study utilizes a single-profile conjoint design (Bansak et al., 2021). That is, participants rate the trustworthiness of fictional university profiles which have randomly assigned levels on the variables of interest, i.e. integrity commitments, integration commitments, and reputation. The strength of the conjoint design is that it allows for the randomization of multiple attributes simultaneously, which allows for the estimation of the effect of any attribute while controlling for all other included attributes. Furthermore, the conjoint design allows for the implementation of multiple ratings per participant, increasing the number of observations.

As with any design, this is not without trade-offs. The most cited trade-offs are the tension between control and cognitive burden, and the limits to participant attention across multiple ratings (Bansak et al., 2021). Having a higher number of attributes allows for additional control, increasing the precision of the treatment effects, but a high number of attributes runs the risk of cognitive overload, introducing noise into the regressions that counteract the gains from increased control. The POIESIS survey experiment assigns random values to six attributes for each profile, a relatively low number of attributes. Additionally, the number of ratings per participant presents a second trade-off between amount of data and respondent fatigue. For the sake of data quality, the POIESIS survey experiment will also opt for a relatively low number of ratings, four ratings per participant.

Among the six attributes, three provide cues on integrity: *Integrity principles*, *special interests*, and *diversity and inclusion*. Two provide cues on integration: *Hearing the public*, and *science communication*. These first five attributes all assign level of commitment in

the same way. They can either take the value of *has strict procedures*, indicating that the university is highly committed to the issue, *follows national recommendations*, indicating that the organization abides by the rules but does not commit itself further, and *lacks procedures* indicating a lack of commitment to the issue. The final attribute provides a cue on *reputation*. This takes a unique form, as we have less interest in how it itself affects trust but are rather interested in whether the effects of integrity and integration are robust to control for reputation, and how reputation cues might moderate the effect of the integrity and integration commitments. This attribute can take five potential values: First, it can be *omitted*, to estimate the effect of the primary attributes without the influence of a reputation cue. Second, it can take an *abstract prestige* value of either *high* or *low*. Finally, it can take a *research content* value, indicating that the university has a particular reputation regarding either *climate* research or *covid* research. Doing so, allows for testing both whether different levels of prestige alter the way in which universities are evaluated, i.e. are people more lenient when evaluating high prestige institutions, as well as the influence of performance in specific value loaded areas of research in climate and covid research.

This generates university profiles that look like the example in Figure 3.1.1 below. Note that both the level and order of the attributes is randomized. Moreover, the attribute and its level are highlighted in bold to make reading easier for study participants.

Figure 3.1.1: Example of a randomly generated university profile from the experiment

How trustworthy do you find this university?

- Is among the **less prestigious** universities in the country
- Has **strict procedures** ensuring **hearing the public** when they are impacted by university research
- **Lacks procedures** on **diversity and inclusion** amongst staff
- Follows **national recommendations** on **conflicts of interests** in research
- Has **strict procedures** to uphold **honesty, transparency, and responsibility** of research
- **Lacks procedures** on **public communication** of the knowledge it produces

Notes: Example university profile. Order and level of attributes randomized for all profiles. Rated on a scale of 0-10.

Participants rate the trustworthiness of the fictional university on a scale from 0 to 10. This exercise is repeated four times, with a newly generated profile presented each time. After participants are done with these ratings, they are then asked to rank which considerations mattered the most for their behaviour in the experimental tasks based on the dimensions of trustworthiness widely used in the literature, that is expertise, benevolence, integrity, and openness (Besley et al., 2021; Besley & Tiffany, 2023; Hendriks et al., 2015). These four dimensions are rewritten into the statements seen in Figure 3.1.1. Respondents are then asked to rank these considerations in order of how influential they were for their trustworthiness evaluations. The initial order (prior to ranking) was randomized to safeguard against order effects.

Figure 3.1.2: Ranking of the influence of dimensions of trustworthiness in the experimental tasks

Please rank how influential the considerations below were in shaping your reaction to the university profiles you just rated:

(Drag statements to rank)

Their willingness to interact with the public

Their level of concern for the good of public

Their commitment to ensure professional standards

Their ability to produce high quality research

Notes: Trustworthiness dimensions presented in a random order prior to ranking.

3.2 Survey flow

Figure 3.2 below shows a graphical representation of the survey flow. The first page of the survey contains the informed consent form (available alongside the entire questionnaire in the appendix, master in English in Appendix 7.1.1, and translations in Appendix 7.1.2-7.1.7). For the sake of demonstrating sample characteristics and balance, and investigating heterogeneous effects, the survey then includes a limited set of background variables. These are grouped into a set of sociodemographic variables (gender, age, education, professional proximity to science) and a set of attitudinal variables (trust in science, trust in political institutions, ideological position, religiosity). Participants are then briefed on the experimental task they are about to perform, being told that “This study seeks to understand what makes people trust universities and

research centres. On the following pages, you will be presented with a series of fictional universities. These have different characteristics. Based on these characteristics, please indicate how trustworthy you would find each university”. This is followed by the conjoint experiment. Each participant rates four randomly generated fictional university profiles. After completing the four rating tasks, participants then rank which theoretical dimensions of trustworthiness (expertise, benevolence, integrity, and openness) was most influential for their ratings. Finally, participants are debriefed, disclosing the research question and providing a final opportunity for withdrawing from the study. Withdrawal at any point in the survey is considered a retraction of consent.

Figure 3.2.1: Survey flow

3.3 Integrity considerations

Throughout the design and implementation phases of the POIESIS survey experiment, utmost care has been taken to minimize harm while simultaneously maximizing research quality and adhering to research integrity and open science principles.

The study is approved by the ethical committee at the School of Business and Social Sciences at Aarhus University. The application contained a description of the study and the ethical considerations discussed in this section. The study was approved by the ethical committee on the June 14th 2024.

The key ethical consideration was whether participants would be subject to any risk and harm. As participants rated fictional universities and were made aware that this was the case in the experiment briefing, no form of deception was employed. As such, it is very unlikely that treatments could have any adverse effects on participants. Participants also received informed consent prior to participation and had to consent to be eligible for

participation (see exact wording in Appendix 7.1.1, and translations in Appendix 7.1.2 through 7.1.7). In addition, participants that did not fully complete the survey were considered to have withdrawn consent and were made aware of this practice. This effectively enabled withdrawal of consent at any time during the survey. In the debriefing, participants were once again made aware of this practice to allow for post-participation retraction of consent. After completion of the survey, however, participants are not identifiable and as such withdrawal of consent after finalized participation is impossible.

To ensure transparency of all components of the research process, the study protocol was made publicly available on the POIESIS Zenodo repository (Fuglsang, 2024) prior to data collection. Additionally, the study was pre-registered, to ensure transparency in the methodological and analytical approach (see details in Appendix 7.2). Moreover, after academic publication of the main findings of the study, the data will be made publicly available. Participants were made aware of this practice in the informed consent form. Prior to publication, the final dataset will only be shared within the POIESIS consortium. The survey was coded in Qualtrics and all data was collected in the Qualtrics system. Access to the raw data was exclusive to Aarhus university, and identifiers (e.g. IP addresses) were not collected to ensure full anonymity. In accordance with Aarhus University guidelines, the data was removed from Qualtrics after the data collection was completed.

3.4 Implementation

The survey experiment was first drafted in English and then translated into local languages of the partner countries by the project partners. The recruitment was done through the panel provider Norstat. All survey coding and data administration was run by Aarhus University. The design and implementation of the study followed the procedure laid out by the study protocol (Fuglsang, 2024), also presented in Table 3.3 below. The first draft of the protocol was written and circulated in May 2024. The study was submitted for ethical approval at Aarhus University and received approval on June 14th, 2024. The questionnaire was developed in the summer of 2024. The master questionnaire was finalized and submitted along with the finalized protocol on August 30th, 2024. The survey was translated and the translated versions were tested by the partners in the seven partner countries (except the UK) throughout September of 2024. After this, the study was preregistered at OSF, see Appendix 7.2, and the survey was fielded in October and November 2024. The writing of this deliverable, including internal review marks the final subtask of Task 2.4.

Table 3.4: Tasks, responsibilities, and timeline for Task 2.4

Task	Partner(s)	Completion
2.4.1: Protocol (draft)	AU, feedback from partners	May
2.4.2: Ethics approval	AU	June
2.4.3: Questionnaire design	AU, feedback from partners	August
2.4.1: Protocol (final)	AU	August
2.4.4: Translation	All partners	September
2.4.5: Survey coding	AU	September
2.4.6: Testing	All partners	September
2.4.7: Preregistration	AU	October
2.4.8: Fielding	AU	November
2.4.9: Analysis	AU, feedback from partners	November
2.4.10: Deliverable D2.4	AU	January

4 Findings

This chapter presents the findings of the POIESIS survey experiment. These follow the procedures outlined in the protocol and preregistration. Section 4.1 presents the characteristics of the sample and experiment across countries. Section 4.2 then presents main results, on which the hypotheses and research questions are evaluated. Finally, section 4.3 contains exploratory analyses to gain further insight into the underlying patterns of the results of the experiment.

The study was run among 400 people of the age of 18 or above in each of the seven POIESIS partner countries. The total survey sample is 2847 participants, due to minor oversampling in some countries. The data was collected through panel provider Norstat in October and November 2024. The sampling was set up with quotas to ensure national representation on Gender and Age, other demographic representation relied on recruitment practices of the panel provider.

All results are based on regressions simultaneously including all attributes and all full sample regressions control for country clustering (country fixed effects and country standard errors). Fixed effects regressions use the `feols()` function from the `fixest` package (Berge et al., 2022), single country regressions use the base `r lm()` function. All analyses are presented in graphical form using `GGplot 2` (Wickham, 2011), `patchwork` (Pedersen, 2024), and `ggrridges` (Wilke, 2024) to produce the figures. Furthermore, for all analyses the trustworthiness measure has been standardized (mean 0, standard deviation 1) within countries. Moderation analyses are performed as split-sample regressions for ease of presentation. Regression outputs for the main analyses are included as tables in Appendix 7.3. Two additional models with further control are available in Appendix 7.3.1. These show that control for rating order does not change results, indicating that learning is not an issue across the repeated ratings. Moreover, including individual fixed effects does not change results, indicating successful randomization.

4.1 Descriptives

The sociodemographic characteristics of the sample can be seen in Figure 4.1.1. Gender is split almost 50/50 in all countries, with a very small minority of non-binary participants (in white in the middle, barely visible due to the low proportion). For Spain, Portugal, and Greece respondents above 65 are underrepresented, due to difficulties in recruiting these groups in online surveys. The educational makeup of the sample generally shows a satisfactory distribution. However, it is worth noting that national educational classifications, especially for Germany and Denmark, do not follow the same scheme as the master questionnaire. As such the apparent imbalance is likely mostly an artefact of

reclassifying the national setups, which were used in translated the surveys, to the general scheme of the merged dataset. Finally, proximity to science is measured through professional involvement with science. Most participants do not work with science, while fewer are involved in various ways. Note that the Greek sample reports a particularly high reported level relation to science. It is uncertain what exactly causes this pattern, though we suspect this to be combination of language and institutional factors.

Figure 4.1.1: Sociodemographic characteristics of participants split by country

Notes: For gender, light is women, dark is men and white (in the middle) is non-binary. Education shows the unified version of the education variable with the levels of: Primary education, Lower secondary education (Middle school), Upper secondary education (High school), Bachelor’s or equivalent level, Master’s or equivalent level, and Doctoral or equivalent level. Proximity to science asks respondents “Are you professionally involved with science?” taking the levels of: Indirectly or occasionally, No/Not really, Yes, I am a science student, Yes, I am a scientist/researcher, and Yes, it is part of my work.

The participants were then asked to indicate their attitudes on four variables: Their trust in science, their trust in political institutions, their ideology on a left-right scale, and their level of religiosity. All of these were recorded on 11-point (0-10) scales. The distributions of these variables across countries can be seen in figure 4.1.2 below. Across all countries trust in science is high, the overall sample mean is 7.6 out of 10. This aligns with existing knowledge on attitudes towards science as an abstract concept (e.g. European Commission, 2021). There is however some slight variation, in that the French sample is ~.8 scale points below the full sample mean. The highest trusting country, Spain, is ~.5 above the sample mean. However, it is uncertain to which degree this variation is the result of actual trust climates, cultures, or an artefact of language or other differences.

Moreover, it should be noted that the distributions of trust in science are highly uniform across countries, with a large group of high trustors and a smaller group of ambivalent people in the middle in most countries.

In contrast to trust in science, trust in political institutions is lower. The mean trust is 4.1 and the variation is also small across countries (highest Denmark 4.8, lowest France 3.4). However, there is clear variation in the modality of the distributions, indicating different landscapes in trust in political institutions across countries. Regarding ideology on a left/right scale, all countries are centred around a centrist position (mean = 5.2), with approximately equal amounts of right- and left-wing participants. Finally, regarding religiosity almost all countries have a considerable proportion of areligious participants (at 0), then a group of agnostics (around 5), and a group indicating varying levels of reported religiosity (i.e. above 5).

Figure 4.1.2: Prior attitudes of participants split by country

Notes: All attitudes are recorded on 0-10 scales, reported as density plots with a bandwidth of .5. For both trust questions, 10 is very high trust, for ideology 10 is very right wing, for religiosity 10 is very religious.

Finally, the distributions on the trustworthiness ratings from the experimental tasks as well as the time spent interacting with the experimental tasks is worth noting. This can be seen in Figure 4.1.3 below. As seen in the first pane, the participants use the entirety of the scale in evaluating the universities, with a mean just above the midpoint at 5.9. This is a bit higher in Spain and Portugal where the mean is around 6.3. For some countries, notably France, there is a tendency to pick the middle category, perhaps indicating that the exercise was seen as either difficult or unengaging for some participants. This later point is also supported by the last two panes. First the rating time (note the exponential

scale on the x-axis), shows that a high proportions of experimental tasks were done very quickly (>10 seconds), which would indicate limited engagement among some participants. Building on this, however, the rating time by rating order (all participants did four ratings) shows how the mean rating time is considerably higher for the first rating than the subsequent. This might indicate that once familiar with the format, rating time reached a natural plateau.

Figure 4.1.3: Trustworthiness ratings of university profiles and rating time in the experimental tasks split by country

Notes: Distributions on the trustworthiness ratings from the experimental tasks, distribution of rating time (note the exponential scale), and mean rating time across the four rating tasks (white on top is first rating, dark blue on bottom is fourth). Note that extreme outliers of rating time of 10 minutes or more are excluded.

4.2 Main analyses

The main analyses aim to answer the hypotheses and research questions:

- H1 Commitment to research integrity in research performing organizations increases trust in science.
- H2 Commitment to societal integration in research performing organizations increases trust in science.
- RQ1 To which degree are effects of integrity and integration consistent across countries?
- RQ2 To which degree are effects of integrity and integration moderated by organization reputation?

The two hypotheses are investigated in full sample regressions simultaneously including all attributes, these are presented in Section 4.2.1. RQ1 and RQ2 are answered through split sample regressions on countries (4.2.2) and the reputation attribute level (4.2.3) respectively.

4.2.1 The effects of research integrity and societal integration

The effects of commitment to integrity and integration on trustworthiness ratings are shown in Figure 4.2.1. For this analysis the reference group for all integrity and integration attributes is “lacks procedures”. For the reputation attribute the reference is when this attribute is omitted. As such, the positive estimates for all integrity and integration attributes indicates that all forms of commitment have a positive effect on trustworthiness perceptions. That is, both levels of commitment, following national recommendations or having strict procedures, produce higher trustworthiness perceptions than the lack of commitment does. This supports both hypotheses H1 and H2.

Figure 4.2.1: Effects of integrity, integration, and reputation on trustworthiness ratings

Notes: Recommendations is “follows national recommendations”, strict is “has strict procedures”. For the five first attributes the reference level is “lacks procedures”, for reputation the reference level is no cue. OLS regressions with country fixed effects and country clustered standard errors. Trustworthiness rating is standardized within countries.

There are, however, several noteworthy patterns to discuss. First, while participants are quite receptive to commitment to all forms of integrity and integration, they clearly do not distinguish between the two kinds of commitment. Across all attributes, the effectiveness of the “national recommendations” and the “strict procedures” are statistically indistinguishable. For all but the “diversity and inclusion” attribute the difference is in the expected direction (strict procedures more effective), but of insignificant magnitude. It should be noted that this finding is consistent with prior research which similarly shows that while the public is sensitive to commitment towards replication when contrasted with the lack thereof, they are less sensitive to the details of replication (Hendriks et al., 2020).

Second, integrity principles (commitment to “Honesty, transparency, and responsibility”) outperforms all the other attributes in its effectiveness. Other than a small positive gap for the conflict-of-interest attribute, the rest of the integrity and integration attributes have approximately the same influence on the trustworthiness evaluation. It could be seen as unexpected that the least concrete attribute causes the largest effect, especially given findings from prior studies of POIESIS that indicate sensitivity to content and context (Entradas et al., 2023). However, this further motivates the conclusion that it is (lack of) commitment to good practice rather than the specificities of this practice which resonates with the public.

Third, it should be noted that the effects of commitment to research integrity and societal integration is robust to control for organizational reputation. Furthermore, integrity and integration are also of comparable or greater magnitude than the effects of reputation. As such, this is evidence supporting the assumptions that the public is sensitive to commitments towards research integrity and societal integration alongside, and potentially over, reputation.

4.2.2 Country differences

RQ1 asks whether the effects seen above are constant across countries. That is, if the experiment is seen as seven separate studies set in different countries would these lead to the same conclusion regarding the effectiveness of institutional commitment towards integrity and integration? This question is investigated in Figure 4.2.2. Given the lack of differences between the two levels of commitment to integrity and integration initiatives found in the analysis of the main effect above, the model is run with a simplified version of the treatment having either lack of commitment (reference) or having one of the two forms of commitment. As such effects below are the effect of having any form of commitment relative to having none. Separate analyses for each country, compared to the full sample analysis, can be seen in Appendix 7.4

Figure 4.2.2: Effects of integrity, integration, and reputation split by country.

Notes: Effect of institutional commitment (either following national recommendations or having strict procedures) compared to “lacks procedures”, and prestige/research compared to no cue. OLS regressions separately run per country. Trustworthiness rating is standardized within countries.

Across all countries all commitments have a positive effect on trustworthiness ratings. Effect sizes and patterns do, however, differ. Regarding the highest performing attribute, integrity principles, the Danish sample is more sensitive to the treatment than participants in the other countries. Both Denmark and the UK are particularly sensitive to commitments towards safeguarding against conflicts of interest, whereas the Greek sample is not very sensitive to this. Commitment towards securing diversity and inclusion among staff has the most grouped results of any of the attributes, with very little cross-cultural variation. Regarding sensitivity to commitment to public hearings, the Greek and

British sample are the least and most sensitive respectively. Finally, public communication commitment produces a considerable spread between the sensitivity across countries, Denmark most sensitive, UK and Greece close behind, and little sensitivity in Spain and Portugal. As such, there is clearly a cultural dimension to how commitment to research integrity and social integration affects trustworthiness perceptions. However, it is equally notable that all commitments matter in all investigated countries.

Turning to the country differences across the reputation cues, results show smaller effects of these treatments in line with the full sample regressions. High prestige receives higher trustworthy ratings than omitting the reputation cue, whereas low prestige does the opposite, and the specific research cues does very little to trustworthiness ratings. It should however be noted that the Portuguese respondents stand out as particularly sensitive to these cues.

4.2.3 The moderating role of reputation

RQ2 asks whether general reputation moderates the effect of the focal attributes concerning integrity and integration. As noted above, the mere inclusion of this attribute in the university profiles does not eliminate the effects of the integrity and integration attributes, which suggests that the main effects are not merely an artefact of reputation. The key interest in this section, however, is whether the reputation attribute moderates the effect of the integrity and integration attributes. This is examined in the split-sample regressions in Figure 4.2.3 below. Again, given the lack of difference between forms of commitment (see Section 4.2.1), the simplified commitment measure is implemented.

Overall, the effects of the integrity and integration attributes are not conditional on whether a reputation cue is provided nor on the level that it takes. Generally, effects of all research integrity and societal integration are very similar across split samples across the reputation variable. Furthermore, interaction models in Appendix 7.3.2 confirm that differences are below conventional thresholds for statistical significance for the vast majority of interaction terms between the integrity/integration attributes and the reputation attribute. As such, reputation is not a notable moderator of institutional commitment to either integrity or integration.

Three minor but noteworthy exceptions should be highlighted. First, the effect of integrity principles when given no reputation cue is slightly higher, indicating that this specific attribute displays the expected reduction in effectiveness. However, even though effects are reduced the effect of the integrity principles attribute remains the highest in the face of reputation cues. Additionally, the effect of the diversity and inclusion attribute is slightly lower when given the high prestige cue, and the effect of the public hearings attribute is lower when given the “covid research” cue. These patterns may indicate that in some instances reputation cues can reduce the effect of integrity and integration cues, or that

some combinations of reputation and commitments affect trustworthiness in a certain way. However, the overall conclusion is that commitment to both research integrity and societal integration is very robust to reputation cues.

Figure 4.2.3: Effects of integrity and integration commitment split by reputation levels

Notes: Effect of institutional commitment (either following national recommendations or having strict procedures) compared to “lacks procedures”. Split sample regressions across levels of the reputation attribute. OLS regressions with country fixed effects and country clustered standard errors. Trustworthiness rating is standardized within countries.

4.3 Exploratory analyses

While the main questions of study are answered by the above analyses, as outlined in the preregistration a series of exploratory analyses are run in addition. These are chosen to gain further insight on potential nuances missed above as well as testing for potential issues. Specifically, these exploratory analyses investigate five additional questions. First, Section 4.3.1 looks at the question of alignment between participants behaviour in the experimental tasks and their rated importance of dimensions of trustworthiness. This is done to align our findings with existing conceptualizations of trustworthiness. In the second and third sections, heterogenous effects across prior attitudes (4.3.2) and socioeconomics (4.3.3) are investigated. Both exploratory analyses are included to

understand whether institutional commitments towards research integrity and societal integration are more relevant for fostering trust for some than others. Fourth, Section 4.3.4 investigates the role of attention and interaction with the experiment by turning to moderation from time taken in the experiment and the random order in which attributes were presented. Finally, Section 4.3.5 shows cross-attribute interactions, to investigate whether the combination of certain commitments lead to larger or smaller effects.

For all of these, the simplified versions of the treatment variables are used. In this simplified treatment variable, both versions of commitment to the research integrity and societal integration attributes (“national recommendations” and “strict procedures”) are collapsed, to investigate the difference between commitment and lack of commitment. This is implemented as both treatments have almost identical effects (see Section 4.2.1).

4.3.1 Comparing effects across importance of trustworthiness dimensions

As noted above, we seek to align our study with existing studies on trust perceptions by incorporating existing conceptualizations of trustworthiness. We do this by investigating whether the main findings of the experiment align with participants own reports of which dimensions of trustworthiness mattered the most for them when rating the universities. To gauge this, participants were asked to rank four dimensions relevant to trust in science. These build on the work of Besley et al. (2021) asking participants to rank which of openness (*their willingness to interact with the public*), benevolence (*their level of concern for the good of the public*), integrity (*their commitment to ensure professional standards*), or expertise (*their ability to produce high quality research*) was the most important.

Figure 4.3.1.1: Ranked importance of trustworthiness dimension in experimental task

Notes: Proportion ranking each of the four trustworthiness dimensions as 1st to 4th most important for how university profiles were ranked.

Overwhelmingly, participants indicate that expertise was the most important dimension for the way they rated the universities trustworthiness, 42 % of the sample indicating that this was the most important, see Figure 4.3.1.1 above. This could be seen as inconsistent with the smaller effects of the reputation cues in the analyses above. However, it might be speculated that some of the integrity attributes, perhaps particularly the integrity principles, might be perceived as a form of expertise. That is, a university which has the ability to secure “honesty, transparency, and responsibility” could be interpreted as a university that produces high quality research. The second most important dimension according to the participants is integrity, which aligns with the finding that integrity principles is the most effectful attribute in all analyses. In fact, 39 % of participants have expertise and integrity as their top two most important characteristics for how they rated the universities. On the opposite end, openness is clearly rated as least important for the trustworthiness ratings, 46 % picking this as the bottom characteristic.

Figure 4.3.1.2: Effects of integrity, integration, and reputation split by most important dimension of trustworthiness

Notes: Effect of institutional commitment (national recommendations or strict procedures) compared to “lacks procedures”, and prestige/research compared to no cue. Split sample regressions across self-rated most important trustworthiness dimension. OLS regressions with country fixed effects and country clustered standard errors. Trustworthiness rating is standardized within countries.

To further investigate these patterns Figure 4.3.1.2 shows the results of regressions split by which trustworthiness dimensions participants rated as the most important for their ratings in the experimental tasks. This allows for assessing whether respondent behaviour in the experiment aligns with self-reported prioritization. Doing so shows, first, that participants who rank integrity or expertise to be most important for their trustworthiness ratings are impacted the most by the university characteristics across the board. Second, as might be expected those who find openness most important are only affected by the two integration items alongside integrity principles, indicating that their behaviour in the experiment mirrors their self-professed priorities. Third, across benevolence, integrity, and expertise, in that order, the effect of prestige does slightly increase, which aligns with an expectation that the more important the output is vis-à-vis motivations the more prestige matters for trustworthiness ratings.

4.3.2 Heterogenous effects across attitudes

Turning to heterogenous effects of the treatments, the first point of interest is the role of prior attitudes in moderating the effects of commitment to integrity and integration. All four attitudes (trust in science, trust in political institutions, left-right ideology, and level of religiosity) were included based on the expectation that they might matter for differences in trustworthiness ratings. To investigate the moderating role of these attitudes, split sample regressions are presented below for each of these attitudes, splitting the sample into two groups, one below the neutral value (5, neither/nor) and one above the neutral value. As such, in these splits participants saying neither/nor, i.e. the middle value, are excluded. This is done for the sake of ease of presentation and has no consequences for the conclusions.

Results show that differences in effect sizes across prior attitudes are generally low, with the notable exception of trust in science. As such, further investigation of this particular variation is presented below. For the three remaining attitudes, trust in political institutions, political ideology, and religion, differences are generally quite small. The two notable differences being that left-wing and areligious respondents are more sensitive to the diversity and inclusion attribute as well as to the integrity principles attribute. Especially the patterns for diversity and inclusion indicate that commitments might be more effectful when they align with individual values.

As noted above, effects of the treatments are notably heterogeneous across prior levels of trust in science. These differences are clear and of considerable magnitude. In fact, for participants who indicate low trust in science, the effects of the treatments are nearly undetectable. Though it should be noted that this group makes up only 5 percent of the total sample, it is notable that this group is seemingly not receptive to differences in university commitments.

Figure 4.3.2.1: Effects of integrity, integration, and reputation split by prior attitudes

Notes: Effect of institutional commitment (national recommendations or strict procedures) compared to “lacks procedures”, and prestige/research compared to no cue. Split sample regressions either low (below 5) or high (above 5) on the prior attitude measures. OLS regressions with country fixed effects and country clustered standard errors. Trustworthiness rating is standardized within countries.

To further investigate this dynamic of heterogenous effects across prior trust in science, Figure 4.3.2.2 below shows local regression estimates (LOESS) for trustworthiness ratings (y-axis) across prior trust in science (x-axis). The mean trustworthiness rating in commitment treatment conditions shown in blue and mean in lack of commitment treatments in red. Mirroring the above, this shows that participants who indicate to have a neutral (neither/nor) or lower level of trust in science prior to the experiment are not sensitive to the integrity and integration commitments. The effect of the treatment, corresponding to the gap between the two lines, is basically non-existent at low levels of prior trust, but appears among participants who have at least some trust in science. This could be read in two ways. First, the effect of integrity and integration commitments are less effective in producing trust among those who lack it to begin with, but quite effectful in bolstering trust in those who are trusting prior to receiving such information. Second,

this could be interpreted as indications that lack of commitment does not further decrease trust among low trusters, but it reduces trustworthiness perceptions among those that trust science in first place, indicating that commitments towards research integrity and societal integrations are needed to maintain trust.

Figure 4.3.2.2: Trustworthiness ratings in experimental groups across trust in science

Notes: Trustworthiness ratings as smooth local regression (LOESS) in the no commitment conditions (red) and the commitment conditions (blue) across levels of prior trust in science.

4.3.3 Heterogeneous effects across sociodemographics

Just like the attitudinal position might matter for sensitivity to the treatments, variation in sensitivity across sociodemographics could also be expected. In this study, we recorded gender, age, education, and professional proximity to science. The overall conclusion from the split sample regressions below, however, is that sociodemographics are not very consequential for receptivity to institutional commitment to integrity and integration.

It should be noted that many sociodemographic groups have a low number of respondents, and that the resulting uncertainty limits the strength of the conclusions regarding heterogeneous effects across sociodemographics. This is particularly important to note given that prior research indicate that specific social groups have specific needs and relations to science (Dawson, 2018; Humm & Schrögel, 2020). Therefore, the results in this section should not be taken to indicate that everyone receives information on institutional commitment in the same way, rather that we do not see systematic variation in how the resulting trustworthiness ratings turn out. Dedicated research would be needed to fully understand these dynamics.

Gender and age splits are shown in Figure 4.3.3.1 below. Note that non-binary respondents are not included in this analysis due to the very low number of participants identifying as such, resulting in extreme uncertainty. The overall pattern for both gender

and age is that neither produce heterogenous effects of the treatment. The one exception that men are less sensitive to commitment to diversity and inclusion than women.

Figure 4.3.3.1: Effects of integrity, integration, and reputation split by gender and age

Notes: Effect of institutional commitment (national recommendations or strict procedures) compared to “lacks procedures”, and prestige/research compared to no cue. Split sample regressions across gender and age. OLS regressions with country fixed effects and country clustered standard errors. Trustworthiness rating is standardized within countries.

Figure 4.3.3.2 shows heterogenous effects across educational levels. It should be noted that both the group holding only primary education and the group holding doctoral degree are very small. Especially for people with only primary education, the smallest group, this means that the estimates are extremely uncertain, and as such this group has been excluded from the figure. The overall pattern is that educational background matters for the effects of some attributes, though the statistical certainty is quite low. For

integrity principles, this does not affect people who hold PhDs but affects everyone else. For the two other integrity attributes, conflicts of interest and diversity and inclusion, the pattern is reversed, and the effect is slightly higher for PhD holders. Finally low prestige seems to only matter for participants with Master’s or PhD degrees.

Figure 4.3.3.2: Effects of integrity, integration, and reputation split by education

Notes: Effect of institutional commitment (national recommendations or strict procedures) compared to “lacks procedures”, and prestige/research compared to no cue. Split sample regressions across unified educational level. OLS regressions with country fixed effects and country clustered standard errors. Trustworthiness rating is standardized within countries.

Finally, participants were asked to indicate their professional proximity to science. Split sample regressions based on this variable are shown in Figure 4.3.3.3. This too produces estimates of considerable statistical uncertainty. Furthermore, other than science students being more sensitive to the climate research cue and science communication commitment, no notable patterns are apparent. As such it seems that being involved with science does not particularly matter for how people are affected by the integration and

integrity profiles of the universities. However, the lack of respondents having close relation to science might also play a role in the uncertainty of these findings.

Figure 4.3.3.3: Effects of integrity, integration, and reputation split by professional proximity to science (Are you professionally involved with science?)

Notes: Effect of institutional commitment (national recommendations or strict procedures) compared to “lacks procedures”, and prestige/research compared to no cue. Split sample regressions across professional proximity to science. OLS regressions with country fixed effects and country clustered standard errors. Trustworthiness rating is standardized within countries.

4.3.4 Time and order effects

The following analyses investigate time spent on interacting with the experiment tasks and the effect of the order of the presentation attributes. This aims to understand, first, the role of attention in the experimental tasks for the results of the experiment. Second, to assess whether learning plays a role in participants behaviour (which would violate assumptions at the basis of repeated ratings). Finally, to understand whether participants are differentially affected by cues based on the order in which they are presented.

Figure 4.3.4.1: Effects of integrity, integration, and reputation split by time spent on experimental task and viewing order

Notes: Effect of institutional commitment (national recommendations or strict procedures) compared to “lacks procedures”, and prestige/research compared to no cue. Split sample regressions across time spent rating and the position in the order of rating tasks. OLS regressions with country fixed effects and country clustered standard errors. Trustworthiness rating is standardized within countries.

The left pane of Figure 4.3.4.1 shows regressions split by how much time respondents spend rating the university profiles. Splits are based on quartiles of time spent. The quarter of participants who spent the least amount of time, spending less than 6.8 seconds, are hardly affected by the treatment. This is not surprising given the very limited interaction with the treatment possible in such a short time. It could be argued that this low engagement group should be excluded from the study. However, it might alternatively be argued that it is very reasonable to expect a large portion of people in the real-world being disengaged with this form of information (or science in general; Losi, 2023). In the design of the study, we aligned with the later argument, and as such, these disengaged participants are included for the sake of realism. The last 75 % of participants, spending more than 6.8 seconds on the ratings, are affected by all integrity and integration attributes indicating that even very brief consideration makes a difference for evaluation.

The right pane in Figure 4.3.4.1 turns to viewing order. All participants rate four fictional universities in the experiment. It might be feared that effect sizes changes across viewing order as this would indicate learning, which would violate the assumptions that form the base of the conjoint design. There are however no signs that effectiveness of the integrity and integration attributes vary significantly across viewing order, though minor changes can be seen for the prestige levels. This latter point is however not a problem for the main interest of the study, the effect of integrity and integration commitments. It should also be noted that if the study had been run as a single-evaluation study, the main conclusions would be unaltered.

Turning to viewing position, i.e. the random placement of the attribute on a university profile, Figure 4.3.4.2 shows how these matter for effect sizes. This is presented both with and without the prestige attribute as this attribute has a considerably different character than the rest. However, both versions clearly show that being lower on the list of attributes hardly changes effect sizes, indicating a similar level of interaction with the attributes regardless of position. As such, participants seem to interact with the full list of university characteristics. They do not latch on to the first and/or last attribute and ignore the rest of the information.

Figure 4.3.4.2: Effect of commitment by position of attribute in the order of university attributes

Notes: Effect of attribute position i.e. was it first, second, etc., in the list of attributes describing any fictional university. The left pane includes the prestige attribute (coded as no cue or cue), right pane excluding prestige due to the different variable characteristic. OLS regressions with country fixed effects and country clustered standard errors. Trustworthiness rating is standardized within countries.

4.3.5 Cross-attribute interactions

Finally, it might be asked whether attributes moderate the effects of each other. To provide an overview of cross-attribute interactions, Figure 4.3.5 shows split samples across all simplified integrity and integration attributes. The general picture emerging from this analysis is that none of the integrity and integration attributes matter dramatically for the effects of the remaining attributes. It might be noted that while moderations among integrity and integration attributes are very minor, some of the reputation attribute values are sensitive to commitment to specific integrity and integration measures. These, naturally, mirror the interactions seen in section 4.2.3, as they show the same moderations from the opposite perspective.

Figure 4.3.5.1: Effects of integrity, integration, and reputation split by integrity and integration attributes

Notes: Effect of institutional commitment (national recommendations or strict procedures) compared to “lacks procedures”, and prestige/research compared to no cue. Split sample regressions across each of the (simplified) integrity and integration attributes. OLS regressions with country fixed effects and country clustered standard errors. Trustworthiness rating is standardized within countries.

5 Discussion and conclusions

The POIESIS survey experiment tests the expectation that institutional commitment to research integrity and societal integration affects trust in science. It does so in a conjoint survey experiment in which respondents rate the trustworthiness of fictional university profiles, which are randomly assigned levels of institutional commitment to research integrity and societal integration.

The main result of the study is that institutional commitment to both research integrity and societal integration affects trustworthiness perceptions. However, participants are not particularly sensitive to the character of the commitment. Participants have nearly identical ratings of “adhering to national recommendations” and “having strict procedures”, but both are rated as more trustworthy than “lacking procedures”. These findings are mirrored across the seven countries investigated, though the patterns in magnitudes of effects differ. Moreover, the effects of such commitments are not significantly diminished by providing information on organization reputation.

The primary finding, that members of the public are sensitive to institutional commitment to integrity and integration, is consistent with the assumptions that POIESIS sets out to test. That is, it does indeed matter whether research organizations commit to research integrity and societal integration when their trustworthiness is evaluated. In fact, all forms of commitment included in the experiment affect trustworthiness ratings and do so independently from one another. Prior studies identify related integrity measures, especially among researchers, as relevant for trust, i.e. replicability (Anvari & Lakens, 2019; Hendriks et al., 2020; Methner et al., 2023; Wingen et al., 2020), special interests in research (Critchley et al., 2015; Critchley, 2008), and open science practices (Rosman et al., 2022). However, this study is the first to turn attention to the commitments of research performing organizations, demonstrating the potential of institutional commitment towards integrity and integration to influence trust.

However, this simple interpretation could naturally be nuanced, and two points of discussion may be of special relevance in understanding the implications of these findings. First, it might be asked whether the results indicate sensitivity to specific integrity and integration commitments or to commitment to doing good as such. That is, what exactly is it that people are reacting to, and does this correspond to what we are assuming? The lack of difference between the effects of “national recommendations” and “strict procedures” suggests that while commitment matters, its form and degree might be less crucial. The pattern of almost equal magnitude of effects of different forms of commitment, other than commitment to integrity principles, hints in the same direction. As such, it might be asked whether what we see is sensitivity to commitment to specific standards of research, or if it is merely sensitivity to good intentions in a more abstract sense. While the simple implication of either interpretation is perhaps similar, institutional commitment to integrity and integration matters for trust, this could challenge assumptions on sensitivity to specific aspects of these commitments. i.e. it might not be

committing to a specific practice (e.g. safeguarding against special interests) that matters, but rather the good intentions inherent to committing to research integrity and societal integration.

The second consideration is the degree to which the results of this study are transferable out of the proverbial laboratory. We show notable effects in the very short term, and while results are clear, the setting is artificial. It should be noted that even among recruited and compensated survey participants, a sizeable amount of about a quarter chooses not to meaningfully engage with the integrity and integration information. This might lead to an underestimation of the influence of such commitments for people who receive this type of information but should also be an indication that this is not a form of information that is naturally engaging. Moreover, given the subject matter of the study, it might also be asked whether participants might alter their behaviour to mirror what they believe we want (demand bias) or to appear as they think is most desirable (social desirability bias). As such, while we clearly demonstrate sensitivity, the breadth and magnitude of such effects are not clearly established. Deeper understanding of the underlying psychological mechanisms for how people make these evaluations and when/whether they receive it requires additional investigation.

The study also tested the potential cross-cultural heterogeneity of effects of institutional commitment to research integrity and societal integration. While translations pose some difficulties in precisely evaluating cultural differences, it seems that sensitivity to integrity and integration cues is universal, at least in the included countries. The exact patterns of magnitude, however, are different. It might rightfully be asked whether different patterns in magnitude are a matter of cultural differences, differences in local science systems, political climates, or any other potential factors. Furthermore, while the countries included represent a wide range in the context of Europe, though with the notable exception of eastern Europe, it might be asked whether these results are applicable to other contexts. Cross-cultural uniformity in large parts of Europe does not equate to generalizability elsewhere, and additional research would be needed to establish the apparent universality of the findings of this study.

The final research question asked whether the effects of commitment towards research integrity and societal integration would be less impactful when respondents simultaneously receive cues on organization reputation. That is, if people are told that the university is good does it then matter whether it does good? The answer to this question, is that integrity and integration clearly matters, even when a reputation cue is given. In fact, whether cues on prestige level or research contents are given hardly matters for the effect sizes of institutional commitment to integrity and integration. The only, but perhaps notable, exception is regarding the principles of integrity, which does perform better when no reputation cue is given. Overall, this finding implies that commitment to research integrity and societal integration is separate and robust to reputation, and notably that respondents do not apply different standards to universities based on university prestige.

Sensitivity to institutional commitment to integrity and integration is not highly differential across individual characteristics included in the experiment. Across attitudinal levels, there are minor differences regarding the diversity and inclusion attribute indicating some value-based differences in sensitivity. Across sociodemographic groups, education and professional proximity to science seems to relate to some differences in effects, but such patterns have high statistical uncertainty. The notable finding regarding heterogeneous effects is the differences in effect sizes across prior trust in science. Specifically, among participants who have low trust in science, i.e. indicate 5 or less on the 11-point trust in science scale prior to the experiment, there is no effect of the integrity and integration commitments. As noted above, this could motivate two interpretations. First, the interpretation that low trust individuals are not sensitive to efforts towards research integrity and societal integration, and that institutional commitments to these therefore cannot produce trust. Second, it could be interpreted as an indication that the lack of commitment to these ideals is detrimental to trust, but only for those who started out trusting science, and that such commitments are therefore crucial to maintaining trust. These two readings are not mutually exclusive, and it should be noted that the low trust participants are a very small percentage of the total sample. However, it is worth noting this difference in sensitivity, as it speaks to the core question of the trust-building and/or -maintaining properties of institutional commitment to research integrity and societal integration.

This study provides evidence for the claim that institutional commitments towards research integrity and societal integration matters for public trust in science. Across countries and in the face of competing cues on organization reputation effects are clear. However, the findings also provide nuances to the discussion of what exactly it is about these commitments that make it to the public understanding of science. Prior results in the POIESIS project suggest that the public is receptive to nuances in forms of commitment to integrity and integration. While the results of the POIESIS survey experiment reiterates sensitivity to institutional commitments towards research integrity and societal integration, it also raises questions on the character of this sensitivity and the degree to which different forms of commitment are really seen as sides to the same issue. The next steps of the POIESIS project will bring together the different streams of evidence to provide more broadly founded discussions on when and how these commitments matter for public trust, and how trust-building and -maintenance may be achieved.

6 References

ALLEA. (2023). The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity – Revised Edition 2023.

Angrist, J. D., & Pischke, J.-S. (2009). Mostly harmless econometrics: An empiricist's companion. Princeton university press. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/j.ctvc4m4j72>

Anvari, F., & Lakens, D. (2019). The replicability crisis and public trust in psychological science. *Comprehensive Results in Social Psychology*, 3(3), 266-286.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/23743603.2019.1684822>

Bansak, K., Hainmueller, J., Hopkins, D. J., & Yamamoto, T. (2021). Conjoint Survey Experiments. In J. N. Druckman & D. P. Green (Eds.), *Advances in Experimental Political Science* (pp. 19-41). Cambridge University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.1017/9781108777919.004>

Bauer, M. W., Behm-Bahtat, A.-S., & Bunt, H. (2023). D1.2: Dataset on core trust items, climate science, and COVID-19. <https://poiesis-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/05/POIESIS-D1.2.pdf>

Berge, L., Krantz, S., & McDermott, G. (2022). Package 'fixest'.
<https://lrberge.github.io/fixest/>

Besley, J. C., Lee, N. M., & Pressgrove, G. (2021). Reassessing the variables used to measure public perceptions of scientists. *Science Communication*, 43(1), 3-32.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/1075547020949547>

Besley, J. C., & Tiffany, L. A. (2023). What are you assessing when you measure “trust” in scientists with a direct measure? *Public Understanding of Science*, 09636625231161302.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/09636625231161302>

Critchley, C., Nicol, D., & Otlowski, M. (2015). The impact of commercialisation and genetic data sharing arrangements on public trust and the intention to participate in biobank research. *Public Health Genomics*, 18(3), 160-172.
<https://doi.org/10.1159/000375441>

Critchley, C. R. (2008). Public opinion and trust in scientists: the role of the research context, and the perceived motivation of stem cell researchers. *Public Understanding of Science*, 17(3), 309-327. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0963662506070162>

Dawson, E. (2018). Reimagining publics and (non) participation: Exploring exclusion from science communication through the experiences of low-income, minority ethnic groups. *Public Understanding of Science*, 27(7), 772-786.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0963662517750072>

- Dubois, M. (2024). D.3.2: Focus Groups – Findings. Exploring Institutional Roles in Fostering Public Trust in Science. <https://poiesis-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/05/POIESIS-D3.2.pdf>
- Entradas, M., Sousa, I., & Yan, F. (2023). D2.2: Public Deliberative Workshops – Findings. https://poiesis-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/10/Deliverable-2.2-PDW-Findings_FINAL.pdf
- European Commission. (2021). Special Eurobarometer 516 – April-May 2021 “European citizens’ knowledge and attitudes towards science and technology” Summary. <https://europa.eu/eurobarometer/surveys/detail/2237>
- Fuglsang, S. (2024). T2.4: Survey experiment protocol. <https://zenodo.org/records/13618104>
- Hendriks, F., Kienhues, D., & Bromme, R. (2015). Measuring Laypeople’s Trust in Experts in a Digital Age: The Muenster Epistemic Trustworthiness Inventory (METI). PLoS ONE, 10(10), e0139309. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0139309>
- Hendriks, F., Kienhues, D., & Bromme, R. (2020). Replication crisis = trust crisis? The effect of successful vs failed replications on laypeople’s trust in researchers and research. Public Understanding of Science, 29(3), 270-288. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0963662520902383>
- Humm, C., & Schrögel, P. (2020). Science for all? Practical recommendations on reaching underserved audiences. Frontiers in Communication, 5, 42. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fcomm.2020.00042>
- Losi, L. (2023). Who engages with science, and how? An empirical typology of Europeans’ science engagement. Public Understanding of Science, 32(6), 798-814. <https://doi.org/10.1177/09636625231164340>
- Mejlgaard, N., Bouter, L. M., Gaskell, G., Kavouras, P., Allum, N., Bendtsen, A.-K., Charitidis, C. A., Claesen, N., Dierickx, K., & Domaradzka, A. (2020). Research integrity: nine ways to move from talk to walk. Nature, 586(7829), 358-360. <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-020-02847-8>
- Methner, N., Dahme, B., & Menzel, C. (2023). The “replication crisis” and trust in psychological science: How reforms shape public trust in psychology. Social Psychological Bulletin, 18, 1-15. <https://doi.org/10.32872/spb.9665>
- Pedersen, T. L. (2024). patchwork: The Composer of Plots. R package version 1.3.0.9000, <https://github.com/thomasp85/patchwork>. <https://patchwork.data-imaginist.com>
- POIESIS consortium. (2021). POIESIS project proposal.
- Rosman, T., Bosnjak, M., Silber, H., Kossmann, J., & Heycke, T. (2022). Open science and public trust in science: Results from two studies. Public Underst Sci, 31(8), 1046-1062. <https://doi.org/10.1177/09636625221100686>

- Ryan, T. K., Mejlgaard, N., & Degn, L. (2021). Organizational patterns of RRI: how organizational properties relate to RRI implementation. *Journal of Responsible Innovation*, 8(2), 320-337. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23299460.2021.1975376>
- Wickham, H. (2011). ggplot2. *Wiley interdisciplinary reviews: computational statistics*, 3(2), 180-185. <https://doi.org/10.1002/wics.147>
- Wilke, C. O. (2024). ggridges: Ridgeline Plots in 'ggplot2'. <https://wilkelab.org/ggridges/>
- Wingen, T., Berkessel, J. B., & Englich, B. (2020). No replication, no trust? How low replicability influences trust in psychology. *Social Psychological and Personality Science*, 11(4), 454-463. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1948550619877412>
- Woolley, R., & Payá, I. M. (2024). D.2.3: Expert Interviews - Findings. https://poiesis-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/09/D2.3_POIESIS.pdf

7 Appendix

7.1 Questionnaires in all languages

All questionnaire translations are available below. Each subheading was presented as a new page. Possible responses are provided as bullet points.

7.1.1 English (Master)

7.1.1.1 Consent

Thank you for your interest in participating in this study.

This study investigates what makes people trust scientific institutions. The survey will take about 10 minutes to complete. The study is a part of the POIESIS project financed by the European Union's horizon Europe programme (HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01) under grant number 101057253. Recruitment is administered by Norstat. The study is led by Aarhus University (Denmark) in collaboration with London School of Economics (UK), Wissenschaft im Dialog (Germany), National Technical University of Athens (Greece), Instituto Universitário de Lisboa (Portugal), Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique (France), and Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Cientificas (Spain).

Data will be fully anonymous, and the researchers behind the study will not be able to identify you or connect you to your responses. If you wish to contact the researchers behind the study, please email research responsible Simon Fuglsang at simon.fuglsang@ps.au.dk.

Data will be administered by Aarhus University in Denmark. Data will be shared among the partner organizations. After publication of the study, the data will be made public to facilitate transparency and reuse. Data will be kept indefinitely but will in no way be traceable back to you, i.e. they will be fully anonymised. Findings will be published in a public report and may be published in one or more research articles.

If you consent to the above please indicate so by clicking "I consent" below.

While answering the survey, you may withdraw your consent at any time by leaving the survey. Any survey that is not completed is treated as having withdrawn consent and will be deleted from the final data. Complete answers will not be traceable back to you; therefore, it will not be possible to delete your answers after completion.

- I consent
- I do not consent

7.1.1.2 Demographics

What is your gender?

- Woman
- Man
- None of the above / Non-binary
- Prefer not to say

What is your age (in full years)?

- [Entered by respondent]

What is your highest level of education?

- Primary education
- Lower secondary education (Middle school)
- Upper secondary education (High school)
- Bachelor's or equivalent level
- Master's or equivalent level
- Doctoral or equivalent level

Are you professionally involved with science?

- Yes, I am a scientist/researcher
- Yes, I am a science student
- Yes, it is part of my work
- Indirectly or occasionally
- No/Not really

7.1.1.3 Attitudes

How much trust do you have in science?

- 0-10 slider
 - (0) Very low level of trust
 - (5) Neither/nor
 - (10) Very high level of trust

How much trust do you have in political institutions?

- 0-10 slider
 - (0) Very low level of trust
 - (5) Neither/nor
 - (10) Very high level of trust

Where do you place yourself on a political left-right scale?

- 0-10 slider
 - (0) Very left wing
 - (5) Neither/nor
 - (10) Very right wing

How religious would you say that you are?

- 0-10 slider
 - (0) Not at all religious
 - (5) Neither/nor
 - (10) Very religious

7.1.1.4 Briefing

This study seeks to understand what makes people trust universities and research centres. On the following pages, you will be presented with a series of fictional universities. These have different characteristics. Based on these characteristics, please indicate how trustworthy you would find each university.

7.1.1.5 Conjoint experiment

How trustworthy do you find this university?

- Respondents rate profiles with one random characteristic from each group, presented in a random order, on a 0-10 slider
 - (0) Very low trustworthiness
 - (5) Neither/nor
 - (10) Very high trustworthiness

Integrity	High	Has strict procedures to uphold honesty, transparency, and responsibility of research
	Neutral	Follows national recommendations on honesty, transparency, responsibility of research
	Low	Lacks procedures regarding honesty, transparency, responsibility of research
Interests	High	Has strict procedures that safeguard against conflicts of interest in research
	Neutral	Follows national recommendations on conflicts of interest in research

	Low	Lacks procedures regarding conflicts of interest in research
Diverse	High	Has strict procedures to secure diversity and inclusion amongst staff
	Neutral	Follows national recommendations on diversity and inclusion amongst staff
	Low	Lacks procedures on diversity and inclusion amongst staff
Hearing	High	Has strict procedures ensuring hearing the public when impacted by university research
	Neutral	Follows national recommendations on hearing the public when impacted by university research
	Low	Lacks procedures regarding hearing the public when impacted by university research
Communication	High	Has strict procedures securing public communication of the knowledge it produces
	Neutral	Follows national recommendations on public communication of the knowledge it produces
	Low	Lacks procedures on public communication of the knowledge it produces
Reputation	Prestige (high)	Is among the most prestigious universities in the country
	Prestige (Low)	Is among the less prestigious universities in the country
	Covid	Played an active role in developing vaccines during the Covid-19 pandemic
	Climate research	Is leading in climate change research

7.1.1.6 Selfrate

Please rank how influential the considerations below were in shaping your reaction to the university profiles you just rated:

(Drag statements to rank)

- Their level of concern for the good of public
- Their willingness to interact with the public
- Their commitment to ensure professional standards
- Their ability to produce high quality research

7.1.1.7 Debrief

Thank you for your participation.

This study investigated how the behaviour of universities and research centres affects trust. In the experiment we randomly assigned levels of research integrity (upholding ethical, legal and professional standards) and societal integration (including and engaging society in research), and university reputation. This was done to investigate the relative weight of these factors in shaping trustworthiness perceptions.

If you wish to retract your consent, you can do so by leaving the survey. If you do so your data will be deleted, and your answer will be considered incomplete. Once you press “next” you will not be identifiable, and you will no longer be able to retract your consent.

7.1.2 German

7.1.2.1 Consent

Vielen Dank für Ihr Interesse, an dieser Studie teilzunehmen.

Diese Studie untersucht, welche Aspekte das Vertrauen der Menschen in Universitäten und Forschungszentren ausmacht. Das Ausfüllen der Umfrage dauert etwa 10 Minuten. Diese Studie ist Teil des POIESIS-Projekts, das durch das Programm Horizon Europe der Europäischen Union (HORISON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01) unter der Förderungsnummer 101057253 finanziert wird. Die Rekrutierung erfolgt durch den Dienstleister Norstat. Die Studie wird von der Universität Aarhus (Dänemark) in Zusammenarbeit mit Wissenschaft im Dialog (Deutschland), dem Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique (Frankreich), der Nationalen Technischen Universität Athen (Griechenland), dem Instituto Universitário de Lisboa (Portugal), der Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas (Spanien) und der London School of Economics (Großbritannien) durchgeführt.

Die Daten werden vollständig anonymisiert. Die Forschenden, die die Studie durchführen, werden weder in der Lage sein, Sie zu identifizieren, noch Ihre Antworten mit Ihnen in Verbindung zu bringen. Wenn Sie mit den beteiligten Forschenden Kontakt aufnehmen möchten, senden Sie bitte eine E-Mail an den Forschungsverantwortlichen Simon Fuglsang unter simon.fuglsang@ps.au.dk.

Die Daten der Studie werden von der Universität Aarhus in Dänemark verwaltet und von den Partnerorganisationen gemeinsam genutzt. Nach Veröffentlichung der Studie werden die Daten freigegeben, um Transparenz zu fördern und eine Wiederverwendung zu ermöglichen. Die Daten werden auf unbestimmte Zeit aufbewahrt, können aber in keiner Weise zu Ihnen zurückverfolgt werden, d.h. sie werden vollständig anonymisiert. Die Ergebnisse werden in einem Bericht veröffentlicht und könnten in einem oder mehreren Forschungsartikeln publiziert werden.

Wenn Sie damit einverstanden sind, bestätigen Sie dies bitte, indem Sie unten auf „Ich stimme zu“ klicken.

Während der Beantwortung der Umfrage können Sie Ihre Zustimmung jederzeit zurückziehen, indem Sie die Umfrage verlassen. Jede nicht abgeschlossene Umfrage wird als Widerruf der Zustimmung behandelt und aus den endgültigen Daten gelöscht. Vollständige Antworten können nicht zu Ihnen zurückverfolgt werden; es ist daher nicht möglich, Ihre Antworten nach Abschluss der Umfrage zu löschen.

- Ich stimme zu
- Ich stimme nicht zu

7.1.2.2 Demographics

Mit welchem Geschlecht identifizieren Sie sich?

- Weiblich
- Männlich
- Keines der oben genannten / nicht-binär
- Ich möchte nicht antworten

Wie alt sind Sie? (bitte tragen Sie eine Zahl ein)

- [Entered by respondent]

Was ist Ihr höchster formaler Bildungsabschluss?

- Grundschulabschluss
- Volks- /Hauptschulabschluss
- Mittlere Reife / Realschulabschluss
- Lehre oder gleichwertige Berufsausbildung
- Fachhochschulreife / Abitur / erweiterte Oberschule
- Bachelorabschluss oder gleichwertig
- Masterabschluss oder gleichwertig
- Doktorgrad / PhD

Haben Sie beruflich mit Wissenschaft zu tun?

- Ja, ich bin Wissenschaftler*in /Forscher*in
- Ja, ich bin Student*in
- Ja, es ist Teil meiner Arbeit
- Indirekt oder gelegentlich
- Nein / Nicht wirklich

7.1.2.3 Attitudes

Wie viel Vertrauen haben Sie in die Wissenschaft?

- 0-10 slider
 - (0) Sehr geringes Vertrauen
 - (5) Weder noch
 - (10) Sehr hohes Vertrauen

Wie viel Vertrauen haben Sie in politische Institutionen?

- 0-10 slider
 - (0) Sehr geringes Vertrauen
 - (5) Weder noch
 - (10) Sehr hohes Vertrauen

Wie würden Sie sich selbst politisch einordnen?

- 0-10 slider
 - (0) Sehr links
 - (5) Weder noch
 - (10) Sehr rechts

Als wie religiös würden Sie sich selbst bezeichnen?

- 0-10 slider
 - (0) Überhaupt nicht religiös
 - (5) Weder noch
 - (10) Sehr religiös

7.1.2.4 Briefing

In dieser Studie geht es darum, zu verstehen, was das Vertrauen der Menschen in Universitäten und Forschungszentren ausmacht. Auf den folgenden Seiten werden Ihnen eine Reihe fiktiver Universitäten vorgestellt, welche unterschiedliche Merkmale haben. Bitte geben Sie an, wie vertrauenswürdig Sie die Universitäten jeweils finden würden und berücksichtigen Sie dabei deren unterschiedlichen Merkmale.

7.1.2.5 Conjoint experiment

Für wie vertrauenswürdig halten Sie diese Universität?

- Respondents rate profiles with one random characteristic from each group, presented in a random order, on a 0-10 slider
 - (0) Sehr wenig vertrauenswürdig
 - (5) Weder noch
 - (10) Sehr stark vertrauenswürdig

Integrity	High	Verfügt über strenge Verfahren zur Gewährleistung von Ehrlichkeit, Transparenz und Verantwortlichkeit in der Forschung
	Neutral	Befolgt nationale Empfehlungen in Bezug auf Ehrlichkeit, Transparenz und Verantwortlichkeit in der Forschung
	Low	Verfügt über keine Verfahren in Bezug auf Ehrlichkeit, Transparenz und Verantwortlichkeit in der Forschung
Interests	High	Verfügt über strenge Verfahren zum Schutz vor Interessenkonflikten in der Forschung

	Neutral	Befolgt nationale Empfehlungen in Bezug auf Interessenkonflikte in der Forschung
	Low	Verfügt über keine Verfahren in Bezug auf Interessenkonflikte in der Forschung
Diverse	High	Verfügt über strenge Verfahren zur Sicherstellung von Vielfalt und Inklusion unter den Mitarbeitenden
	Neutral	Befolgt nationale Empfehlungen zu Vielfalt und Inklusion der Mitarbeitenden
	Low	Verfügt über keine Verfahren zu Vielfalt und Inklusion unter den Mitarbeitenden
Hearing	High	Verfügt über strenge Verfahren zur Sicherstellung der Einbeziehung der Öffentlichkeit, wenn diese von der Forschung der Universität betroffen ist
	Neutral	Befolgt nationale Empfehlungen zur Einbeziehung der Öffentlichkeit, wenn diese von der Forschung der Universität betroffen ist
	Low	Verfügt über keine Verfahren zur Einbeziehung der Öffentlichkeit, wenn diese von der Forschung der Universität betroffen ist
Communication	High	Verfügt über strenge Verfahren zur Sicherstellung der öffentlichen Kommunikation des von ihr produzierten Wissens
	Neutral	Befolgt nationale Empfehlungen in Bezug auf die öffentliche Kommunikation des von ihr produzierten Wissens
	Low	Verfügt über keine Verfahren in Bezug auf die öffentliche Kommunikation des von ihr produzierten Wissens
Reputation	Prestige (high)	Gehört zu den renommiertesten Universitäten des Landes
	Prestige (Low)	Gehört zu den weniger renommierten Universitäten des Landes
	Covid	Spielte eine aktive Rolle bei der Entwicklung von Impfstoffen während der Covid-19-Pandemie
	Climate research	Ist führend in der Forschung zum Klimawandel

7.1.2.6 Selfrate

Bitte ordnen Sie die nachfolgenden Merkmale nach der Stärke des Einflusses, den diese für Sie persönlich bei der Bewertung der verschiedenen Hochschulprofile hatten. Sie können dafür die einzelnen Aussagen in die von Ihnen gewünschte Rangfolge ziehen.

- Die Sorge der Universitäten um das Wohl der Allgemeinheit
- Die Bereitschaft der Universitäten zur Interaktion mit der Öffentlichkeit
- Das Engagement der Universitäten zur Sicherstellung professioneller Standards
- Die Fähigkeit der Universitäten, qualitativ hochwertige Forschung zu produzieren

7.1.2.7 Debrief

Wir danken Ihnen für Ihre Teilnahme an der Studie.

In dieser Studie wurde untersucht, wie das Verhalten von Universitäten das Vertrauen in diese Institutionen beeinflusst. In dem Experiment wurden den Universitätsprofilen nach dem Zufallsprinzip verschiedene Stufen wissenschaftlicher Integrität (d.h. die Einhaltung ethischer, rechtlicher und professioneller Standards) und öffentlicher Beteiligung am Wissenschaftsprozess (d.h. die Einbeziehung und Beteiligung der Gesellschaft an der Forschung) sowie unterschiedliche Reputationen zugewiesen. Dadurch sollte untersucht werden, wie diese Faktoren die Wahrnehmung der Vertrauenswürdigkeit der Universitäten beeinflussen.

Wenn Sie Ihre Zustimmung zur Teilnahme an der Studie zurückziehen möchten, können Sie die Umfrage jetzt verlassen. In diesem Fall werden Ihre Daten gelöscht, und Ihre Antwort wird als unvollständig gewertet. Sobald Sie auf "Weiter" klicken, sind Sie und Ihre Daten nicht mehr identifizierbar. Sie können Ihre Einwilligung dann nicht mehr zurückziehen.

7.1.3 Danish

7.1.3.1 Consent

Tak for din interesse i at deltage i denne undersøgelse.

Studiet undersøger, hvad der får folk til at stole på universiteter og forskningscentre. Undersøgelsen vil tage ca. 10 minutter at gennemføre. Undersøgelsen er en del af POIESIS-projektet, der er finansieret af EU's Horizon Europe-program (HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01) under bevillingsnummer 101057253. Rekrutteringen administreres af Norstat. Undersøgelsen ledes af Aarhus Universitet (Danmark) i samarbejde med London School of Economics (UK), Wissenschaft im Dialog (Tyskland), National Technical University of Athens (Grækenland), Instituto Universitário de Lisboa (Portugal), Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique (Frankrig) og Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas (Spanien).

Data vil være helt anonyme, og forskerne bag undersøgelsen vil ikke kunne identificere dig eller forbinde dig med dine svar. Hvis du ønsker at kontakte forskerne bag undersøgelsen, bedes du sende en e-mail til forskningsansvarlig Simon Fuglsang på simon.fuglsang@ps.au.dk.

Data vil blive administreret af Aarhus Universitet. Data vil blive delt mellem partnerorganisationerne. Efter offentliggørelsen af undersøgelsen vil data blive offentliggjort for at facilitere gennemsigtbarhed og datagenbrug. Data vil blive opbevaret på ubestemt tid, men vil på ingen måde kunne spores tilbage til dig. Resultaterne vil blive offentliggjort i en offentlig rapport og kan blive offentliggjort i en eller flere forskningsartikler.

Hvis du giver dit samtykke til ovenstående, bedes du angive det ved at klikke på ”Jeg giver samtykke” nedenfor.

Under din besvarelse, kan du til enhver tid trække dit samtykke tilbage ved at forlade undersøgelsen. Enhver undersøgelse, der ikke er afsluttet, behandles som om, du har trukket dit samtykke tilbage og vil blive slettet fra det endelige dataset. Fuldendte besvarelser vil ikke kunne spores tilbage til dig; derfor vil det ikke være muligt at slette dine svar, efter du har fuldendt spørgeskemaet.

- Jeg giver samtykke
- Jeg giver ikke samtykke

7.1.3.2 Demographics

Hvad er dit køn?

- Kvinde
- Mand
- Ingen af de ovenstående /non-binær
- Ønsker ikke at svare

Hvad er din alder (i hele år)?

- [Entered by respondent]

Hvad er dit højeste uddannelsesniveau?

- Folkeskole
- Gymnasial uddannelse (f.eks. stx, hf, eux)
- Erhvervsuddannelse
- Bachelors (kort-mellemlang videregående)
- Kandidat (lang videregående)
- PhD (eller anden forskeruddannelse)

Er du professionelt involveret med videnskab?

- Ja, jeg er forsker
- Ja, jeg studerer videnskab
- Ja, det er en del af mit arbejde
- Indirekte, eller nogle gange
- Nej/Ikke rigtigt

7.1.3.3 Attitudes

Hvor meget tillid har du til videnskab?

- 0-10 slider
 - (0) Meget lavt niveau af tillid
 - (5) Hverken/eller
 - (10) Meget højt niveau af tillid

Hvor meget tillid har du til politiske institutioner?

- 0-10 slider
 - (0) Meget lavt niveau af tillid
 - (5) Hverken/eller
 - (10) Meget højt niveau af tillid

Hvor placerer du dig selv på en politisk højre-venstre skala?

- 0-10 slider
 - (0) Meget venstreorienteret
 - (5) Hverken/eller
 - (10) Meget højreorienteret

Hvor religiøs vil du sige, at du er?

- 0-10 slider
 - (0) Overhovedet ikke religiøs
 - (5) Hverken/eller
 - (10) Meget religiøs

7.1.3.4 Briefing

Denne undersøgelse forsøger at forstå, hvad der får folk til at stole på universiteter og forskningscentre. På de følgende sider vil du blive præsenteret for en række fiktive universiteter. Disse har forskellige karakteristika. Angiv venligst, hvor tillidsvækkende du finder disse universiteter baseret på disse karakteristika.

7.1.3.5 Conjoint experiment

Hvor tillidsvækkende finder du dette universitet?

- Respondents rate profiles with one random characteristic from each group, presented in a random order, on a 0-10 slider
 - (0) Slet ikke tillidsvækkende
 - (5) Hverken/eller
 - (10) Meget tillidsvækkende

Integrity	High	Har strenge procedurer for at opretholde ærlighed, gennemsigtighed, og ansvarlighed i forskning
	Neutral	Følger nationale anbefalinger omkring ærlighed, gennemsigtighed, og ansvarlighed i forskning
	Low	Har ikke procedurer omkring ærlighed, gennemsigtighed, og ansvarlighed i forskning
Interests	High	Har strenge procedurer der beskytter imod interessekonflikter i forskning
	Neutral	Følger nationale anbefalinger omkring interessekonflikter i forskning
	Low	Har ikke procedurer omkring interessekonflikter i forskning
Diverse	High	Har strenge procedurer der sikrer diversitet og inklusion blandt deres medarbejdere.
	Neutral	Følger nationale anbefalinger omkring diversitet og inklusion blandt deres medarbejdere
	Low	Har ikke procedurer omkring diversitet og inklusion blandt deres medarbejdere
Hearing	High	Har strenge procedurer der sikrer, at offentligheden bliver hørt, når universitetets forskning påvirker dem
	Neutral	Følger nationale anbefalinger om hvorvidt offentligheden bliver hørt, når universitetets forskning påvirker dem
	Low	Har ikke procedurer om hvorvidt offentligheden bliver hørt, når universitetets forskning påvirker dem
Communication	High	Har strenge procedurer der sikrer offentlig kommunikation af den viden, universitetet producerer
	Neutral	Følger nationale anbefalinger omkring offentlig kommunikation af den viden universitetet producerer

	Low	Har ikke procedurer omkring offentlig kommunikation af den viden universitetet producerer
Reputation	Prestige (high)	Er blandt de mest prestige_fulde universiteter i landet
	Prestige (Low)	Er blandt de mindre prestige_fulde universiteter i landet
	Covid	Spillede en aktiv rolle i at udvikle vacciner under Covid-19 pandemien
	Climate research	Er ledende indenfor forskning i klimaforandringer

7.1.3.6 Selfrate

Ranger venligst de nedenstående overvejelser efter, hvor relevante de var for dine reaktioner til de universitetsprofiler, du lige har vurderet:

(Træk i udtalelserne for at rangere)

- Deres bekymring for offentlighedens ve og vel
- Deres villighed til at interagere med offentligheden
- Deres dedikation til at sikre professionelle standarder
- Deres evne til at producere forskning af høj kvalitet

7.1.3.7 Debrief

Tak for din deltagelse.

Dette studie undersøgte, hvordan universiteters og forskningscentres adfærd påvirker tillid. I eksperimentet tildelte vi tilfældige niveauer af forskningsintegritet (opretholdelse af etiske, juridiske og professionelle standarder), samfundsmæssig integration (inddragelse og engagement af samfundet i forskning), og universitetets omdømme. Dette blev gjort for at undersøge den relative vægt af disse faktorer, når folk danner troværdighedsopfattelser.

Hvis du ønsker at trække dit samtykke tilbage, kan du gøre det ved at forlade undersøgelsen nu. Hvis du gør det, vil dine data blive slettet, og dit svar vil blive betragtet som ufuldstændigt. Når du trykker på "næste", vil du ikke kunne identificeres, og du vil ikke længere kunne trække dit samtykke tilbage.

7.1.4 Spanish

7.1.4.1 Consent

Gracias por su interés en participar en este estudio.

Este estudio investiga los factores que hacen que la gente confíe en las universidades y centros de investigación. Completar la encuesta le llevará unos 10 minutos. El estudio forma parte del proyecto POIESIS financiado por el programa Horizonte Europa de la Unión Europea (HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01) con número de referencia 101057253. Norstat es la organización encargada del reclutamiento de los participantes. El estudio está coordinado por la Universidad de Aarhus (Dinamarca) en colaboración del Consejo Superior Superior de Investigaciones Científicas (España), el Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique (Francia), Wissenschaft im Dialog (Alemania), la Universidad Técnica Nacional de Atenas (Grecia), el Instituto Universitário de Lisboa (Portugal) y la London School of Economics (Reino Unido).

Los datos obtenidos en esta encuesta serán totalmente anónimos y el equipo de investigación del estudio no podrá identificarle ni relacionarle con sus respuestas. Si desea ponerse en contacto con el equipo de investigación del estudio, envíe un correo electrónico al responsable de la investigación Simon Fuglsang (simon.fuglsang@ps.au.dk).

Los datos obtenidos en esta encuesta serán tratados por la Universidad de Aarhus (Dinamarca) y se compartirán con las organizaciones colaboradoras del proyecto (mencionadas anteriormente). Tras la publicación del estudio, los datos se harán públicos por motivos de transparencia y para facilitar su reutilización. Los datos se conservarán indefinidamente, pero en ningún caso se podrá rastrear su vinculación con usted, es decir, serán totalmente anónimos. Los resultados se publicarán en un informe público y podrán aparecer en uno o varios artículos de investigación.

Si acepta lo anterior, indíquelo a continuación haciendo clic en «Acepto».

Puede retirar su consentimiento en cualquier momento abandonando la encuesta. Se considerará que se ha retirado el consentimiento de toda encuesta que no se complete. Las encuestas incompletas se eliminarán de los datos finales. No será posible vincular las respuestas de las encuestas completas con la persona que las aportó y, por tanto, no será posible borrar sus respuestas una vez finalizadas.

- Acepto
- No acepto

7.1.4.2 Demographics

¿Cuál es su género?

- Femenino
- Masculino

- Ninguno de los anteriores / no binario
- Prefiero no contestar

¿Qué edad tiene (en años)?

- [Entered by respondent]

¿Cuál es tu nivel superior de formación?

- Educación primaria
- Educación secundaria
- Bachillerato
- Grado Universitario o equivalente
- Master Universitario o equivalente
- Doctorado o equivalente

¿Tiene vinculación profesional con la ciencia?

- Sí, soy científico/investigador
- Sí, soy estudiante de ciencias
- Sí, es parte de mi trabajo
- Indirectamente u ocasionalmente
- No /No realmente

7.1.4.3 Attitudes

¿Cuánto confía en la ciencia?

- 0-10 slider
 - (0) Nivel muy bajo de confianza
 - (5) Nivel medio
 - (10) Nivel muy alto de confianza

¿Cuánto confía en las instituciones políticas?

- 0-10 slider
 - (0) Nivel muy bajo de confianza
 - (5) Nivel medio
 - (10) Nivel muy alto de confianza

¿Dónde se sitúa usted en la escala política izquierda-derecha?

- 0-10 slider
 - (0) Muy de izquierdas
 - (5) Intermedio
 - (10) Muy de derechas

¿Hasta qué punto diría que es usted religioso?

- 0-10 slider
 - (0) Nada religioso
 - (5) Intermedio
 - (10) Muy religioso

7.1.4.4 Briefing

Este estudio pretende entender qué hace que la gente confíe en las universidades y centros de investigación. En las siguientes pantallas se presentan una serie de universidades ficticias con diferentes características. En función de estas características, indique qué grado de confianza le inspiraría cada universidad

7.1.4.5 Conjoint experiment

¿Qué grado de confianza le inspira esta universidad?

- Respondents rate profiles with one random characteristic from each group, presented in a random order, on a 0-10 slider
 - (0) Nivel de confianza muy bajo
 - (5) Nivel medio
 - (10) Nivel de confianza muy alto

Integrity	High	Tiene procedimientos estrictos para mantener la honestidad, la transparencia y la responsabilidad de la investigación.
	Neutral	Sigue las recomendaciones nacionales sobre honestidad, transparencia y responsabilidad de la investigación
	Low	Carece de procedimientos sobre honestidad, transparencia y responsabilidad de la investigación
Interests	High	Tiene procedimientos estrictos que protegen contra los conflictos de interés en la investigación
	Neutral	Sigue las recomendaciones nacionales sobre conflictos de interés en la investigación
	Low	Carece de procedimientos sobre conflictos de interés en la investigación
Diverse	High	Tiene procedimientos estrictos para garantizar la diversidad y la inclusión entre el personal
	Neutral	Sigue las recomendaciones nacionales sobre diversidad y la inclusión del personal

	Low	Carece de procedimientos sobre diversidad y la inclusión entre el personal
Hearing	High	Tiene procedimientos estrictos que garantizan la escucha a la ciudadanía cuando se ve afectada por la investigación universitaria
	Neutral	Sigue las recomendaciones nacionales sobre escucha a la ciudadanía cuando se ve afectada por la investigación universitaria
	Low	Carece de procedimientos de escucha a la ciudadanía cuando se ve afectada por la investigación universitaria
Communication	High	Tiene procedimientos estrictos que garantizan la comunicación a la ciudadanía de los conocimientos que produce
	Neutral	Sigue las recomendaciones nacionales sobre comunicación a la ciudadanía de los conocimientos que produce
	Low	Carece de procedimientos sobre comunicación a la ciudadanía de los conocimientos que produce
Reputation	Prestige (high)	Se encuentra entre las universidades más prestigiosas del país
	Prestige (Low)	Se encuentra entre las universidades menos prestigiosas del país
	Covid	Desempeñó un papel activo en el desarrollo de vacunas durante la pandemia de Covid-19
	Climate research	Lidera la investigación sobre el cambio climático

7.1.4.6 Selfrate

Indique en qué medida han influido las siguientes consideraciones en su reacción ante los perfiles de las universidades que acaba de valorar:

(Arrastre las frases para ordenarlas por orden de importancia)

- Su nivel de preocupación por el bien público
- Su disposición a interactuar con el público
- Su compromiso de garantizar la calidad profesional

- Su capacidad para producir investigación de alta calidad

7.1.4.7 Debrief

Gracias por su participación.

Este estudio explora cómo afecta el comportamiento de las universidades y los centros de investigación en la confianza que la ciudadanía deposita en ellos. En el experimento se asignaron aleatoriamente diferentes niveles de integridad investigadora (respeto de las normas éticas, legales y profesionales) y de integración social (inclusión y participación de la sociedad en la investigación), así como de reputación universitaria. Se hizo así para investigar el peso relativo de estos factores en la configuración de las percepciones de confianza.

Si desea retractarse de su consentimiento, puede hacerlo abandonando la encuesta. Si lo hace, sus datos se borrarán y su respuesta se considerará incompleta. Una vez que pulse «Siguiente» no podrá ser identificado y ya no podrá retractarse de su consentimiento.

7.1.5 French

7.1.5.1 Consent

Nous vous remercions de votre intérêt pour cette étude.

Cette étude porte sur les raisons qui poussent les gens à faire confiance aux universités et aux centres de recherche. Il vous faudra environ 10 minutes pour répondre à l'enquête. L'étude fait partie du projet POIESIS financé par le programme Horizon Europe de l'Union européenne (HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01) sous le numéro de subvention 101057253. Le recrutement est géré par Norstat. L'étude est dirigée par l'université d'Aarhus (Danemark) en collaboration avec le Centre national de la recherche scientifique (France), Wissenschaft im Dialog (Allemagne), l'université technique nationale d'Athènes (Grèce), l'Instituto Universitário de Lisboa (Portugal), l'Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas (Espagne) et la London School of Economics (Royaume-Uni).

Les données seront totalement anonymes et les chercheurs à l'origine de l'étude ne seront pas en mesure de vous identifier ou de vous relier à vos réponses. Si vous souhaitez contacter les chercheurs à l'origine de l'étude, veuillez envoyer un courriel au responsable de la recherche, Simon Fuglsang, à l'adresse simon.fuglsang@ps.au.dk.

Les données seront gérées par l'université d'Aarhus au Danemark. Les données seront partagées entre les organisations partenaires. Après la publication de l'étude, les données seront rendues publiques afin de faciliter la transparence et la réutilisation. Les données seront conservées indéfiniment mais ne permettront en aucun cas de remonter jusqu'à vous, c'est-à-dire qu'elles seront entièrement anonymisées. Les résultats seront publiés dans un rapport public et pourront faire l'objet d'un ou plusieurs articles de recherche.

Si vous consentez à ce qui précède, veuillez l'indiquer en cliquant sur « Je consens » ci-dessous.

Pendant que vous répondez à l'enquête, vous pouvez retirer votre consentement à tout moment en quittant l'enquête. Si vous ne répondez pas à l'enquête, vous serez considéré comme ayant retiré votre consentement et vous serez supprimé des données finales. Les réponses complètes ne permettront pas de remonter jusqu'à vous ; il ne sera donc pas possible de supprimer vos réponses une fois qu'elles auront été complétées.

- Je consens
- Je ne consens pas

7.1.5.2 Demographics

Etes-vous...?

- Une femme
- Un homme
- Aucun des deux / non binaire
- Je préfère ne pas le dire

Quel âge avez-vous ? (en année)

- [Entered by respondent]

Quel est votre niveau d'étude le plus élevé ?

- Enseignement primaire
- Enseignement secondaire (collège)
- Enseignement secondaire (lycée)
- Baccalauréat ou niveau équivalent
- Master ou niveau équivalent
- Doctorat ou niveau équivalent

Etes-vous professionnellement en lien avec la science ?

- Oui, je suis un scientifique / un chercheur
- Oui, je suis étudiant en sciences
- Oui, cela fait partie de mon travail

- Indirectement ou occasionnellement
- Non / pas vraiment

7.1.5.3 Attitudes

Quel est votre niveau de confiance dans la science ?

- 0-10 slider
 - (0) Un très faible niveau de confiance
 - (5) Ni l'un ni l'autre
 - (10) Un très haut niveau de confiance

Quel est votre niveau de confiance dans les institutions politiques ?

- 0-10 slider
 - (0) Un très faible niveau de confiance
 - (5) Ni l'un ni l'autre
 - (10) Un très haut niveau de confiance

Où vous situez-vous sur un axe politique allant de gauche à droite ?

- 0-10 slider
 - (0) A l'extrême gauche
 - (5) Ni l'un ni l'autre
 - (10) A l'extrême droite

Vous considérez-vous comme étant religieux ?

- 0-10 slider
 - (0) Pas du tout religieux
 - (5) Ni l'un ni l'autre
 - (10) Très religieux

7.1.5.4 Briefing

Cette recherche s'interroge sur ce qui conduit les gens à accorder leur confiance aux établissements de recherche et d'enseignement supérieur. Les pages suivantes présentent une série d'universités fictives. Celles-ci ont des caractéristiques différentes. Sur la base de ces caractéristiques, veuillez indiquer dans quelle mesure vous trouveriez chacune de ces universités digne de confiance.

7.1.5.5 Conjoint experiment

Dans quelle mesure trouvez-vous cette université digne de confiance ?

- Respondents rate profiles with one random characteristic from each group, presented in a random order, on a 0-10 slider
 - (0) Très faible niveau de confiance

- o (5) Ni l'un ni l'autre
- o (10) Niveau de confiance très élevé

Integrity	High	Dispose de procédures strictes pour garantir l'honnêteté, la transparence et la responsabilité de la recherche
	Neutral	Respecte les recommandations nationales en matière d'honnêteté, de transparence et de responsabilité de la recherche
	Low	Manque de procédures concernant l'honnêteté, la transparence et la responsabilité de la recherche
Interests	High	Dispose de procédures strictes pour éviter les conflits d'intérêts dans la recherche
	Neutral	Respecte les recommandations nationales sur les conflits d'intérêts dans la recherche
	Low	Manque de procédures concernant les conflits d'intérêts dans la recherche
Diverse	High	Dispose de procédures strictes pour garantir la diversité et l'inclusion au sein du personnel
	Neutral	Respecte les recommandations nationales concernant la diversité et l'inclusion au sein du personnel
	Low	Manque de procédures concernant la diversité et l'inclusion au sein du personnel
Hearing	High	Dispose de procédures strictes garantissant l'écoute du public en cas d'impact de la recherche universitaire
	Neutral	Respecte les recommandations nationales sur l'écoute du public en cas d'impact de la recherche universitaire
	Low	Manque de procédures garantissant l'écoute du public en cas d'impact de la recherche universitaire
Communication	High	Dispose de procédures strictes garantissant la communication publique des connaissances qu'elle produit
	Neutral	Respecte les recommandations nationales sur la communication publique des connaissances qu'elle produit
	Low	Manque de procédures sur la communication publique des connaissances produites

Reputation	Prestige (high)	Fait partie des universités les plus prestigieuses du pays
	Prestige (Low)	Fait partie des universités les moins prestigieuses du pays
	Covid	A joué un rôle dans le développement de vaccins lors de la pandémie de Covid-19
	Climate research	Est à la tête de la recherche sur le changement climatique

7.1.5.6 Selfrate

Veillez indiquer dans quelle mesure les considérations ci-dessous ont influencé votre réaction aux profils des universités que vous venez d'évaluer :

(Faire glisser les affirmations pour les classer)

- Leur degré d'intérêt pour le bien du public
- Leur volonté d'interagir avec le public
- Leur engagement à respecter les normes professionnelles
- Leur capacité à produire des recherches de haute qualité

7.1.5.7 Debrief

Nous vous remercions de votre participation.

Cette étude s'est intéressée à la manière dont le comportement des universités et des centres de recherche affecte la confiance. Dans l'expérience, nous avons attribué au hasard des niveaux d'intégrité de la recherche (respect des normes éthiques, juridiques et professionnelles) et d'intégration sociétale (inclusion et engagement de la société dans la recherche), ainsi que la réputation de l'université. Ceci afin d'étudier le poids relatif de ces facteurs dans la perception de la confiance.

Si vous souhaitez retirer votre consentement, vous pouvez le faire en quittant l'enquête. Dans ce cas, vos données seront supprimées et votre réponse sera considérée comme étant incomplète. Une fois que vous aurez appuyé sur « suivant », vous ne serez plus identifiable et vous ne pourrez plus retirer votre consentement

7.1.6 Greek

7.1.6.1 Consent

Ευχαριστούμε για το ενδιαφέρον σας να συμμετάσχετε σε αυτή την έρευνα.

Αυτή η μελέτη διερευνά τι κάνει τους ανθρώπους να εμπιστεύονται τα πανεπιστήμια και τα ερευνητικά κέντρα. Για την ολοκλήρωση της έρευνας θα χρειαστείτε περίπου 10 λεπτά. Η μελέτη αποτελεί μέρος του ερευνητικού προγράμματος POIESIS, που χρηματοδοτείται από τον Ορίζοντα Ευρώπη της Ευρωπαϊκής Επιτροπής (θεματική περιοχή: HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01), με αριθμό χρηματοδότησης 101057253. Η διαχείριση της διαδικασίας προσέλκυσης συμμετεχόντων στην παρούσα έρευνα γίνεται από την ηλεκτρονική πλατφόρμα Norstat. Της παρούσας έρευνας ηγείται το Aarhus University (Δανία) και διεξάγεται σε συνεργασία με το Εθνικό Μετσόβιο Πολυτεχνείο (Ελλάδα), το Wissenschaft im Dialog (Γερμανία), το Instituto Universitário de Lisboa (Πορτογαλία), το Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique (Γαλλία), την Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Cientificas (Ισπανία) και το London School of Economics (Μεγάλη Βρετανία).

Τα δεδομένα που θα συλλεγούν από την παρούσα έρευνα θα είναι πλήρως ανώνυμα και οι ερευνητές που θα την διεξαγάγουν δεν θα μπορούν να σας αναγνωρίσουν ή να σας συνδέσουν με τις απαντήσεις σας. Εάν επιθυμείτε να επικοινωνήσετε με τους ερευνητές που θα διεξαγάγουν την έρευνα, παρακαλούμε στείλτε email στον υπεύθυνο έρευνας Simon Fuglsang (simon.fuglsang@ps.au.dk) του Aarhus University (Δανία).

Η διαχείριση των δεδομένων θα γίνει από το Aarhus University (Δανία). Τα δεδομένα θα κοινοποιηθούν μεταξύ των συνεργαζόμενων οργανισμών του ερευνητικού προγράμματος POIESIS. Μετά τη δημοσίευση της μελέτης, τα δεδομένα θα δημοσιοποιηθούν για λόγους διαφάνειας και επαναχρησιμοποίησής τους. Τα δεδομένα αυτά θα διατηρηθούν επ' αόριστον, αλλά είναι πλήρως ανώνυμα. Τα ευρήματα της παρούσας έρευνας θα δημοσιευθούν σε δημόσια έκθεση (παραδοτέο) και ενδέχεται να δημοσιευθούν σε ένα ή περισσότερα ερευνητικά άρθρα.

Εάν συμφωνείτε με τα παραπάνω, δηλώστε τη συγκατάθεσή σας το κάνοντας κλικ στο «Συναινώ» παρακάτω.

Μπορείτε να αποσύρετε τη συγκατάθεσή σας και να αποχωρήσετε από την έρευνα ανά πάσα στιγμή, ακόμα και ενώ απαντάτε στην έρευνα. Οποιαδήποτε έρευνα δεν έχει ολοκληρωθεί αντιμετωπίζεται ως ανάκληση συγκατάθεσης και θα διαγραφεί από τα τελικά δεδομένα. Οι πλήρεις απαντήσεις θα είναι πλήρως ανώνυμες, δηλαδή δεν θα μπορεί να ανιχνευτεί ποιος τις έχει δώσει. Συνεπώς, δεν θα είναι δυνατή η διαγραφή των απαντήσεών σας μετά την ολοκλήρωση της έρευνας.

- Συναινώ
- Δεν συναινώ

7.1.6.2 Demographics

Ποιο είναι το φύλο σας;

- Γυναίκα
- Άντρας
- Κανένα από τα παραπάνω/Μη δυαδικό φύλο
- Προτιμώ να μην απαντήσω

Ποια είναι η ηλικία σας (σε πλήρη έτη);

- [Entered by respondent]

Ποιο είναι το ανώτατο επίπεδο σπουδών σας;

- Πρωτοβάθμια εκπαίδευση
- Γυμνάσιο
- Λύκειο
- Πτυχίο Πανεπιστημίου ή αντίστοιχος τίτλος
- Μεταπτυχιακός τίτλος σπουδών ή αντίστοιχος τίτλος
- Διδακτορικό ή αντίστοιχος τίτλος

Έχετε εμπλακεί με την επιστήμη σε επαγγελματικό επίπεδο;

- Ναι, είμαι επιστήμονας/ερευνητής
- Ναι, είμαι φοιτητής
- Ναι, αποτελεί μέρος της εργασίας μου
- Εμμέσως ή περιστασιακώς
- Όχι

7.1.6.3 Attitudes

Πόσο εμπιστεύεστε την επιστήμη;

- 0-10 slider
 - (0) Πολύ χαμηλό επίπεδο εμπιστοσύνης
 - (5) Κανένα από τα δύο
 - (10) Πολύ υψηλό επίπεδο εμπιστοσύνης

Πόσο εμπιστεύεστε τους πολιτικούς θεσμούς;

- 0-10 slider
 - (0) Πολύ χαμηλό επίπεδο εμπιστοσύνης
 - (5) Κανένα από τα δύο
 - (10) Πολύ υψηλό επίπεδο εμπιστοσύνης

Ποια είναι η πολιτική σας τοποθέτηση στην κλίμακα αριστεράς-δεξιάς;

- 0-10 slider
 - (0) Άκρα αριστερά
 - (5) Κανένα από τα δύο
 - (10) Άκρα δεξιά

Πόσο θρήσκος πιστεύετε ότι είστε;

- 0-10 slider
 - (0) Καθόλου θρήσκος
 - (5) Κανένα από τα δύο
 - (10) Πολύ θρήσκος

7.1.6.4 Briefing

Αυτή η μελέτη διερευνά τι κάνει τους ανθρώπους να εμπιστεύονται τα πανεπιστήμια και τα ερευνητικά κέντρα. Στις επόμενες σελίδες, θα σας παρουσιαστεί μια σειρά από υποθετικά πανεπιστήμια, με διαφορετικά χαρακτηριστικά. Με βάση αυτά τα χαρακτηριστικά, υποδείξετε πόσο αξιόπιστο θα θεωρούσατε κάθε πανεπιστήμιο.

7.1.6.5 Conjoint experiment

Πόσο αξιόπιστο βρίσκετε αυτό το πανεπιστήμιο;

- Respondents rate profiles with one random characteristic from each group, presented in a random order, on a 0-10 slider
 - (0) Πολύ χαμηλό επίπεδο αξιοπιστίας
 - (5) Κανένα από τα δύο
 - (10) Πολύ υψηλό επίπεδο αξιοπιστίας

Integrity	High	Διαθέτει αυστηρές διαδικασίες για την τήρηση της εντιμότητας , της διαφάνειας και της υπευθυνότητας της έρευνας
	Neutral	Ακολουθεί εθνικές συστάσεις σχετικά με την εντιμότητα , τη διαφάνεια , την υπευθυνότητα της έρευνας
	Low	Δεν διαθέτει διαδικασίες σχετικά με την εντιμότητα , τη διαφάνειας και την υπευθυνότητα της έρευνας
Interests	High	Διαθέτει αυστηρές διαδικασίες που προστατεύουν από την έρευνα από συγκρούσεις συμφερόντων

	Neutral	Ακολουθεί εθνικές συστάσεις σχετικά με συγκρούσεις συμφερόντων στην έρευνα
	Low	Δεν διαθέτει διαδικασίες που σχετίζονται με συγκρούσεις συμφερόντων στην έρευνα
Diverse	High	Διαθέτει αυστηρές διαδικασίες για τη διασφάλιση της διαφορετικότητας και της ένταξης στο προσωπικό
	Neutral	Ακολουθεί εθνικές συστάσεις σχετικά με τη διασφάλιση της διαφορετικότητας και της ένταξης στο προσωπικό
	Low	Δεν διαθέτει διαδικασίες για τη διασφάλιση της διαφορετικότητας και της ένταξης στο προσωπικό
Hearing	High	Διαθέτει αυστηρές διαδικασίες που διασφαλίζουν ότι το ίδρυμα αφουγκράζεται το ευρύ κοινό όταν το δεύτερο επηρεάζεται από την πανεπιστημιακή έρευνα
	Neutral	Ακολουθεί εθνικές συστάσεις που διασφαλίζουν ότι το ίδρυμα αφουγκράζεται το ευρύ κοινό όταν το δεύτερο επηρεάζεται από την πανεπιστημιακή έρευνα
	Low	Δεν διαθέτει διαδικασίες που διασφαλίζουν ότι το ίδρυμα αφουγκράζεται το ευρύ κοινό όταν το δεύτερο επηρεάζεται από την πανεπιστημιακή έρευνα
Communication	High	Διαθέτει αυστηρές διαδικασίες που διασφαλίζουν την δημόσια επικοινωνία της παραγόμενης γνώσης από το ίδρυμα
	Neutral	Ακολουθεί εθνικές συστάσεις που διασφαλίζουν την δημόσια επικοινωνία της παραγόμενης γνώσης από το ίδρυμα
	Low	Δεν διαθέτει διαδικασίες που διασφαλίζουν την δημόσια επικοινωνία της παραγόμενης γνώσης από το ίδρυμα
Reputation	Prestige (high)	Είναι μεταξύ των πιο ευυπόληπτων πανεπιστημίων της χώρας
	Prestige (Low)	Είναι μεταξύ των λιγότερο ευυπόληπτων πανεπιστημίων της χώρας
	Covid	Είχε ενεργό ρόλο στην ανάπτυξη των εμβολίων κατά τη διάρκεια της πανδημίας του COVID-19
	Climate research	Είναι πρωτοπόρο στην έρευνα επάνω στην κλιματική αλλαγή

7.1.6.6 Selfrate

Παρακαλούμε κατατάξετε πόσο επιδραστικές ήταν οι παρακάτω σκέψεις στη διαμόρφωση των απαντήσεών σας στα πανεπιστημιακά προφίλ που μόλις βαθμολογήσατε:

Σύρετε τις παρακάτω δηλώσεις για να τις κατατάξετε

- Το επίπεδο ενδιαφέροντός τους για το καλό του ευρύτερου κοινού
- Η προθυμία τους να αλληλεπιδράσουν με το ευρύ κοινό
- Η δέσμευσή τους στη διασφάλιση υψηλών επαγγελματικών προτύπων
- Η ικανότητά τους να παραγάγουν έρευνα υψηλής ποιότητας

7.1.6.7 Debrief

Σας ευχαριστούμε για τη συμμετοχή σας.

Η παρούσα μελέτη διερεύνησε τον τρόπο με τον οποίο η συμπεριφορά των πανεπιστημίων και των ερευνητικών κέντρων επηρεάζει την εμπιστοσύνη. Στο πείραμα αναθέσαμε τυχαία επίπεδα ακεραιότητας της έρευνας (υποστηρίζοντας τα ηθικά, νομικά και επαγγελματικά πρότυπα) και την κοινωνική ενσωμάτωση (συμπεριλαμβανομένης και της συμμετοχής της κοινωνίας στην έρευνα) και της φήμης του πανεπιστημίου. Αυτό έγινε για να διερευνηθεί η σχετική βαρύτητα αυτών των παραγόντων στη διαμόρφωση αντιλήψεων για την αξιοπιστία.

Εάν επιθυμείτε να ανακαλέσετε τη συγκατάθεσή σας, μπορείτε να το κάνετε αποχωρώντας από την έρευνα. Εάν το κάνετε, τα δεδομένα σας θα διαγραφούν και η απάντησή σας θα θεωρηθεί ελλιπής. Μόλις πατήσετε "επόμενο" δεν θα είστε πια αναγνωρίσιμοι και δεν θα μπορείτε πλέον να ανακαλέσετε τη συγκατάθεσή σας.

7.1.7 Portuguese

7.1.7.1 Consent

Obrigado pelo seu interesse em participar neste estudo.

Este estudo investiga a confiança pública nas universidades e centros de investigação. O inquérito demorará cerca de 10 minutos a ser preenchido. O estudo faz parte do projeto POIESIS, financiado pelo programa Horizonte Europa da União Europeia (HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01) com o número 101057253. O recrutamento de participantes é gerido pela Norstat.

O estudo é conduzido pela Aarhus University (Dinamarca) em colaboração com o Iscte - Instituto Universitário de Lisboa (Portugal), Wissenschaft im Dialog (Alemanha),

National Technical University of Athens (Grécia), Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique (França), Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Cientificas (Espanha) e London School of Economics (Reino Unido).

Os dados serão totalmente anónimos e os investigadores responsáveis pelo estudo não poderão identificá-lo/a ou associá-lo/a às suas respostas. Se desejar contactar os investigadores responsáveis pelo estudo, pode enviar um e-mail para o responsável pela investigação, Simon Fuglsang: simon.fuglsang@ps.au.dk.

Os dados serão administrados pela Aarhus University, na Dinamarca, e partilhados entre as organizações parceiras. Após a publicação do estudo, os dados serão tornados públicos para transparência e reutilização. Os dados serão mantidos indefinidamente, mas não serão rastreáveis até si, ou seja, serão totalmente anónimos. As conclusões serão publicadas num relatório público e poderão ser publicadas num ou mais artigos científicos.

Indique o seu consentimento clicando em “Eu aceito”.

Enquanto responde ao inquérito, pode retirar o seu consentimento em qualquer momento, abandonando o inquérito. Qualquer inquérito que não seja completado é considerado como tendo sido retirado o consentimento e será apagado dos dados finais. As respostas completas não serão rastreáveis até si; por conseguinte, não será possível apagar as suas respostas após a sua conclusão.

- Aceito
- Não aceito

7.1.7.2 Demographics

Qual é o seu género?

- Mulher
- Homem
- Nenhum dos anteriores/não binário
- Prefiro não responder

Qual é a sua idade (em anos)?

- [Entered by respondent]

Qual é o nível de escolaridade mais elevado que concluiu com êxito?

- 1.º ciclo do Ensino Básico
- 2.º ciclo do Ensino Básico
- 3.º ciclo do Ensino Básico

- Ensino Secundário
- Licenciatura ou equivalente
- Mestrado ou equivalente
- Doutoramento ou equivalente

Está profissionalmente ligado à ciência?

- Sim, sou cientista/investigador
- Sim, sou estudante de ciências
- Sim, é parte do meu trabalho
- Indireta ou ocasionalmente
- Não

7.1.7.3 Atitudes

Qual é o seu nível de confiança na ciência?

- 0-10 slider
 - (0) Nível de confiança muito baixo
 - (5) Nem muito baixo nem muito alto
 - (10) Nível de confiança muito alto

Qual é o seu grau de confiança nas instituições políticas?

- 0-10 slider
 - (0) Nível de confiança muito baixo
 - (5) Nem muito baixo nem muito alto
 - (10) Nível de confiança muito alto

Onde é que se situa numa escala de esquerda-direita política?

- 0-10 slider
 - (0) Muito à esquerda
 - (5) Nem muito à esquerda nem muito à direita
 - (10) Muito à direita

Até que ponto se considera religioso/a?

- 0-10 slider
 - (0) Não sou religioso/a de todo
 - (5) Nem um nem outro
 - (10) Muito religioso/a

7.1.7.4 Briefing

Este estudo pretende compreender a confiança pública nas universidades e centros de investigação. De seguida, ser-lhe-ão apresentadas universidades fictícias, com diferentes características. Com base nessas características, por favor indique o seu grau de confiança em cada uma dessas universidades

7.1.7.5 Conjoint experiment

Em que medida considera esta universidade confiável?

- Respondents rate profiles with one random characteristic from each group, presented in a random order, on a 0-10 slider
 - (0) Nível de confiabilidade muito baixo
 - (5) Nem um nem outro
 - (10) Nível de confiabilidade muito Elevado

7.1.7.6 Selfrate

Por favor, ordene a influência que as considerações abaixo tiveram na sua reação aos perfis das universidades que acabou de classificar:

(Ordene as frases, arrastando-as)

- seu nível de preocupação com o bem do público
- A sua vontade de interagir com o público
- seu compromisso em garantir padrões profissionais
- A sua capacidade de produzir investigação de elevada qualidade

7.1.7.7 Debrief

Obrigado pela sua participação.

Este estudo investigou a forma como o comportamento das universidades e dos centros de investigação afeta a confiança. Na experiência, atribuímos aleatoriamente níveis de integridade da investigação (manutenção de normas éticas, legais e profissionais) e de integração social (inclusão e envolvimento da sociedade na investigação), bem como a reputação da universidade. O objetivo era investigar o peso relativo destes fatores na formação das perceções de confiança.

Se desejar retirar o seu consentimento, pode fazê-lo abandonando o inquérito. Se o fizer,

os seus dados serão apagados e a sua resposta será considerada incompleta. Uma vez que clique 'próximo', não será identificado e não poderá retirar o seu consentimento'

7.2 Pre-registration

The study was preregistered at OSF (<https://osf.io/yj9hw>). All of the information from the preregistration can also be seen below, with “no response questions excluded”:

STUDY INFORMATION

Hypotheses

H1: Higher research integrity in research performing organizations increases trust in science

H2: More societal integration in research performing organizations increases trust in science

RQ1: Are the effects of integrity and integration consistent across countries?

RQ2: Are the effects of integrity and integration moderated by organization reputation?

DESIGN PLAN

Study type

Experiment - A researcher randomly assigns treatments to study subjects, this includes field or lab experiments. This is also known as an intervention experiment and includes randomized controlled trials.

Study design

The study is a survey experiment employing a conjoint design. In this participants rate fictive university profiles that are assigned random values on six attributes presented in a random order. The experiment utilizes a single profile design (i.e. one university is rated at a time), and participants each perform four rating tasks.

SAMPLING PLAN

Existing Data

Registration prior to creation of data

Data collection procedures

400 participants recruited in each of the 7 partner organization countries (DE, DK, ES, FR, GR, PT, UK). Recruitment through Norstat.

Sample size

2800 (400*7)

Variables

Manipulated variables

Profiles have 6 randomly assigned attributes. Three which are designed to manipulate perceptions of research integrity, two manipulating perceptions of societal integration, and one manipulating prestige:

- (integrity h1) Honesty, transparency, and responsibility
- (integrity h1) Conflicts of interest
- (integrity h1) Diversity and inclusion
- (integration h2) Hearing the public
- (integration h2) Public communication
- prestige

For the first five attributes, on integrity and integration, these can take the values of high (strict procedures), neutral (national recommendations) or low (lacks recommendations). The final attribute, prestige, is included to investigate how other reputation indicators interact with the focal attributes. In a third of the profiles, this takes no value and is omitted. In a third it takes an abstract prestige value of either high prestige or low prestige. In the final third it take a research content value of either climate research or covid resaerch.

Measured variables

Demographics

- gender
- age
- education
- professional proximity to science

Attitudes

- trust in science
- trust in political institutions
- left-right ideology
- religiosity

Post-survey

- self-reported importance of trustworthiness factors (expertise, integrity, benevolence, openness)

ANALYSIS PLAN

Statistical models

Hypotheses 1 and 2 will be evaluated on the basis of multiple regression simultaneously including all manipulated attributes and country level fixed effects. Research questions 1 and 2 will be evaluated on the basis of per country regressions (RQ1) and split sample regressions across the three versions of the prestige attribute (RQ2).

Exploratory analysis

- Relationship between self-rated importance of trustworthiness factors and experiment behavior.
- Heterogeneous effects across demographic and attitudinal variables.
- Investigation of the role of order and time, as a proxy for attention.
- Cross-attribute interactions.

7.3 Regression outputs for main analyses

7.3.1 Main regressions

	Main	+ control for order	+ individual FE
Integrity principles (lacks commitment)			
National recommendations	0.470*** (0.040)	0.471*** (0.040)	0.474*** (0.055)
Strict procedures	0.511*** (0.039)	0.511*** (0.039)	0.518*** (0.053)
Special interests (lacks commitment)			
National recommendations	0.227** (0.057)	0.227** (0.057)	0.241* (0.067)
Strict procedures	0.297** (0.057)	0.297** (0.057)	0.295** (0.066)
Diversity and inclusion (lacks commitment)			
National recommendations	0.203*** (0.022)	0.203*** (0.022)	0.221*** (0.024)
Strict procedures	0.189*** (0.020)	0.189*** (0.020)	0.225*** (0.020)
Hearing the public (lacks commitment)			
National recommendations	0.210*** (0.029)	0.210*** (0.029)	0.233** (0.040)
Strict procedures	0.238*** (0.039)	0.238*** (0.039)	0.267*** (0.035)
Science communication (lacks commitment)			
National recommendations	0.195** (0.033)	0.195** (0.033)	0.177*** (0.022)
Strict procedures	0.223*** (0.032)	0.223*** (0.031)	0.217*** (0.025)
Reputation (no cue)			
Prestige (high)	0.145** (0.030)	0.145** (0.029)	0.120** (0.028)
Prestige (low)	-0.167*** (0.022)	-0.167*** (0.022)	-0.147*** (0.024)
Research (climate)	0.094* (0.029)	0.094* (0.029)	0.108** (0.026)
Research (covid)	0.056 (0.041)	0.056 (0.040)	0.055 (0.037)
Order (first)			
Second		-0.099** (0.017)	-0.099** (0.019)
Third		-0.104** (0.021)	-0.105** (0.025)
Fourth		-0.101** (0.023)	-0.101** (0.026)
Num.Obs.	11388	11388	11388
R2	0.108	0.109	0.624
R2 Adj.	0.106	0.108	0.498
Country fixed effects	✓	✓	✓
Individual fixed effects			✓

7.3.2 Per country regressions

	DE	DK	ES	FR	GR	PT	UK
(Intercept)	-0.799*** (0.084)	-1.348*** (0.080)	-0.753*** (0.088)	-0.769*** (0.089)	-0.751*** (0.083)	-0.967*** (0.087)	-1.249*** (0.085)
Integrity principles (lacks)							
recommendations	0.379*** (0.059)	0.617*** (0.055)	0.366*** (0.058)	0.378*** (0.059)	0.459*** (0.056)	0.570*** (0.058)	0.542*** (0.056)
strict	0.464*** (0.059)	0.723*** (0.055)	0.493*** (0.059)	0.394*** (0.059)	0.518*** (0.056)	0.518*** (0.058)	0.458*** (0.057)
Special interests (lacks)							
recommendations	0.211*** (0.059)	0.429*** (0.055)	0.093 (0.058)	0.205*** (0.060)	0.065 (0.056)	0.185** (0.058)	0.445*** (0.056)
strict	0.292*** (0.059)	0.496*** (0.055)	0.208*** (0.058)	0.212*** (0.060)	0.130* (0.056)	0.270*** (0.058)	0.527*** (0.056)
Diversity and inclusion (lacks)							
recommendations	0.132* (0.059)	0.266*** (0.055)	0.214*** (0.058)	0.166** (0.060)	0.147** (0.056)	0.271*** (0.058)	0.231*** (0.056)
strict	0.187** (0.059)	0.209*** (0.055)	0.262*** (0.059)	0.109+ (0.059)	0.214*** (0.056)	0.200*** (0.058)	0.139* (0.056)
Hearing the public (lacks)							
recommendations	0.188** (0.059)	0.263*** (0.055)	0.199*** (0.058)	0.185** (0.060)	0.088 (0.056)	0.210*** (0.058)	0.327*** (0.057)
strict	0.185** (0.059)	0.307*** (0.055)	0.281*** (0.058)	0.203*** (0.059)	0.096+ (0.056)	0.206*** (0.058)	0.409*** (0.056)
Science communication (lacks)							
recommendations	0.145* (0.059)	0.335*** (0.055)	0.094 (0.058)	0.170** (0.060)	0.285*** (0.056)	0.125* (0.058)	0.208*** (0.057)
strict	0.207*** (0.059)	0.318*** (0.055)	0.139* (0.059)	0.200*** (0.060)	0.273*** (0.056)	0.116* (0.058)	0.327*** (0.057)
Reputation (no cue)							
prestige (high)	0.134+ (0.072)	0.128+ (0.067)	0.084 (0.072)	0.123+ (0.073)	0.183** (0.068)	0.282*** (0.071)	0.050 (0.069)
prestige (low)	-0.195** (0.072)	-0.159* (0.067)	-0.261*** (0.071)	-0.090 (0.073)	-0.167* (0.068)	-0.200** (0.071)	-0.115+ (0.069)
research (climate)	0.144* (0.072)	0.082 (0.067)	0.000 (0.072)	0.071 (0.073)	0.009 (0.069)	0.165* (0.071)	0.190** (0.069)
research (covid)	-0.062 (0.072)	0.096 (0.067)	0.008 (0.072)	0.074 (0.073)	-0.063 (0.068)	0.211** (0.071)	0.132+ (0.069)
Num.Obs.	1600	1600	1620	1600	1760	1604	1604
R2	0.090	0.213	0.092	0.068	0.097	0.125	0.167
R2 Adj.	0.082	0.206	0.084	0.060	0.089	0.117	0.160

7.3.3 Cross-reputation interactions

	a1	a2	a3	a4	a5	all
Integrity principles (lacks)						
recommendations	0.536*** (0.028)	0.470*** (0.040)	0.471*** (0.040)	0.469*** (0.039)	0.471*** (0.039)	0.535*** (0.028)
strict	0.615*** (0.037)	0.510*** (0.039)	0.512*** (0.039)	0.510*** (0.038)	0.511*** (0.039)	0.615*** (0.037)
Special interests (lacks)						
recommendations	0.228** (0.057)	0.225* (0.084)	0.227** (0.057)	0.226** (0.057)	0.227** (0.057)	0.224* (0.083)
strict	0.295** (0.057)	0.318** (0.063)	0.296** (0.057)	0.295** (0.057)	0.297** (0.057)	0.313** (0.062)
Diversity and inclusion (lacks)						
recommendations	0.204*** (0.022)	0.204*** (0.022)	0.197*** (0.031)	0.203*** (0.022)	0.203*** (0.022)	0.198*** (0.030)
strict	0.190*** (0.020)	0.189*** (0.020)	0.229** (0.039)	0.188*** (0.020)	0.189*** (0.020)	0.229** (0.039)
Hearing the public (lacks)						
recommendations	0.208*** (0.030)	0.209*** (0.029)	0.210*** (0.029)	0.270** (0.046)	0.210*** (0.030)	0.270** (0.046)
strict	0.237*** (0.039)	0.237*** (0.039)	0.238*** (0.039)	0.277*** (0.040)	0.237*** (0.039)	0.279*** (0.040)
Science communication (lacks)						
recommendations	0.194** (0.033)	0.194** (0.033)	0.194** (0.033)	0.195** (0.033)	0.184** (0.038)	0.183** (0.037)
strict	0.222*** (0.032)	0.223*** (0.031)	0.224*** (0.032)	0.223*** (0.032)	0.236** (0.043)	0.236** (0.043)
Reputation (no cue)						
prestige (high)	0.210*** (0.035)	0.178*** (0.024)	0.201* (0.055)	0.207** (0.053)	0.115** (0.030)	0.330** (0.067)
prestige (low)	-0.067 (0.040)	-0.176* (0.048)	-0.162* (0.061)	-0.125* (0.047)	-0.159* (0.050)	-0.024 (0.081)
research (climate)	0.163** (0.042)	0.073 (0.051)	0.087 (0.050)	0.076 (0.049)	0.085 (0.057)	0.106 (0.118)
research (covid)	0.163** (0.034)	0.089 (0.052)	0.066 (0.059)	0.170* (0.059)	0.094+ (0.043)	0.379** (0.087)
Integrity principles						
recommend*highprestige	-0.052* (0.016)					-0.052* (0.017)
strict*highprestige	-0.140* (0.053)					-0.137* (0.055)
recommend*lowprestige	-0.114 (0.067)					-0.115 (0.066)
strict*lowprestige	-0.186** (0.046)					-0.189** (0.046)
recommend*climateresaerch	-0.099** (0.019)					-0.097** (0.018)
strict*climateresaerch	-0.106* (0.037)					-0.104* (0.034)

	a1	a2	a3	a4	a5	all
recommend*covidresaerch	-0.125+ (0.056)					-0.133* (0.054)
strict*covidresaerch	-0.192* (0.075)					-0.203* (0.070)
Special interests						
recommend*highprestige		-0.002 (0.057)				0.001 (0.058)
strict*highprestige		-0.101+ (0.043)				0.027 (0.059)
recommend*lowprestige		0.021 (0.062)				0.021 (0.069)
strict*lowprestige		0.007 (0.056)				-0.032 (0.077)
recommend*climateresaerch		0.018 (0.066)				-0.097+ (0.043)
strict*climateresaerch		0.042 (0.062)				0.012 (0.056)
recommend*covidresaerch		-0.022 (0.080)				0.046 (0.062)
strict*covidresaerch		-0.076 (0.050)				-0.088 (0.051)
Diversity and inclusion						
recommend*highprestige			-0.024 (0.059)			-0.024 (0.059)
strict*highprestige			-0.145+ (0.072)			0.006 (0.100)
recommend*lowprestige			0.006 (0.104)			0.045 (0.064)
strict*lowprestige			-0.023 (0.069)			0.011 (0.051)
recommend*climateresaerch			0.044 (0.064)			-0.145+ (0.069)
strict*climateresaerch			-0.024 (0.067)			-0.019 (0.070)
recommend*covidresaerch			0.013 (0.057)			-0.023 (0.067)
strict*covidresaerch			-0.043 (0.065)			-0.050 (0.062)
Hearing the public						
recommend*highprestige				-0.104+ (0.046)		-0.105* (0.041)
strict*highprestige				-0.080 (0.064)		-0.084 (0.051)
recommend*lowprestige				-0.081 (0.050)		0.017 (0.074)
strict*lowprestige				-0.045 (0.071)		-0.198* (0.063)
recommend*climateresaerch				0.017 (0.073)		-0.083 (0.063)
strict*climateresaerch				0.034 (0.051)		-0.048 (0.068)

	a1	a2	a3	a4	a5	all
recommend*covidresaerch				-0.189*		0.031
				(0.064)		(0.051)
strict*covidresaerch				-0.152*		-0.162*
				(0.057)		(0.060)
Science communication						
recommend*highprestige					0.069	0.066
					(0.050)	(0.046)
strict*highprestige					0.021	0.001
					(0.055)	(0.060)
recommend*lowprestige					0.001	0.017
					(0.062)	(0.058)
strict*lowprestige					-0.024	-0.023
					(0.087)	(0.061)
recommend*climateresaerch					0.020	0.019
					(0.057)	(0.056)
strict*climateresaerch					0.008	-0.024
					(0.059)	(0.088)
recommend*covidresaerch					-0.027	0.009
					(0.058)	(0.059)
strict*covidresaerch					-0.084+	-0.084*
					(0.036)	(0.034)
Num.Obs.	11388	11388	11388	11388	11388	11388
R2	0.109	0.108	0.108	0.109	0.108	0.111
R2 Adj.	0.106	0.106	0.106	0.106	0.106	0.106
FE: country	X	X	X	X	X	X

7.4 Figure 4.2.1, results per country

POIESIS survey experiment, ES

POIESIS survey experiment, FR

POIESIS survey experiment, GR

POIESIS survey experiment, PT

POIESIS survey experiment, UK

7.5 Reputation interactions with non-simplified treatments

